

**PREPAREDNESS OF TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS FOR THE
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR TEACHERS:
A MIXED-METHOD STUDY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 8

Pages: 1245-1272

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2811

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14567767

Manuscript Accepted: 12-06-2024

Preparedness of Teacher Education Students for the Licensure Examination for Teachers: A Mixed-Method Study

Jeanne I. Bersabal,* Evelyn E. Cañete

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to describe the lived experiences of fourth-year teacher education students in a local college regarding their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing convergent parallel approach. The Participants of the study were fourth-year students enrolled in Competency Skills Appraisal 1. There were 89 students who were randomly selected for the quantitative and 14 for the qualitative: 7 for in-depth interview and 7 for focus group discussion which were purposively selected. The researcher conducted thematic analysis to examine the qualitative data. This involved recording participants' responses, organizing them, and reducing them into themes through coding and refining the codes during qualitative data analysis. In the quantitative phase, specific tools were applied, including the mean to determine the average participants' responses and the standard deviation to measure the variation in survey answers. Based on the result of the study, it was determined that the level of preparedness of fourth-year teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers is very high. Additionally, the qualitative phase of the study uncovered the lived experiences and coping strategies of fourth-year teacher education students regarding their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. Based on participants' responses, 8 essential themes emerged. The results of the qualitative and quantitative research converge when they are corroborated.

Keywords: *licensure examination for teachers, mixed-method, convergent-parallel, fourth-year teacher education students, philippines*

Introduction

Teacher Education is one of the most sought-after occupations in the Philippines. The fundamental requirement for individuals aspiring to become teachers is the successful completion of a state examination. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) highlighted how crucial it is to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in order to meet the rising demand for top-notch education both domestically and internationally. However, passing the licensure examination for teachers requires a great deal of work and preparation in order to become a professional teacher. The goal of every graduating student is to become a qualified teacher. Still, they can only be formally acknowledged as such if they pass the Professional Regulation Commission's (PRC) teacher license exam and graduate with the qualifications needed to be professional teachers. All policymakers, including teacher educators, have advocated for numerous preparations and have closely connected this to practice (Chua et al., 2019).

Consequently, undergraduate students enrolled in education programs who wish to become licensed educators are required to pass a licensure examination for teachers. However, in the United States, specifically in Massachusetts, research revealed that students' lack of commitment to their review sessions, as evidenced by their unwillingness to work long hours, a tendency to compromise the quality of their work, and poor time management habits, such as failing to stick to a consistent study schedule, not spreading out study time effectively, and not using structured goal setting, negatively affects their preparation for the licensure examination. These findings led the researchers to conclude that a lack of commitment and poor timemanagement became significant hindrances to their success in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers (Jenset et al., 2018).

In the Philippines, specifically in the public universities in Northern Philippines show that Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) disclosed a dismal rating since their LET mean performance both in General Education and Professional Education are below the passing mark. It was revealed that students face inadequate resources, lack of effective study habits, and limited access to quality preparatory programs, which significantly affect their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. It requires thorough preparation from both the College of Education staff and, most importantly, the students. (Maramag et al., 2020).

The study urgently requires research attention to assess the preparedness of teacher education students for licensure examinations. Therefore, this study is timely and necessary as its results can influence the future of teacher education students in their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers making it a crucial endeavor for educators, administrators, and students alike. On the other hand, the study holds social relevance because the information can be used to improve teacher education programs and to develop more effective support mechanisms for students as they prepare for the Licensure Examination for Teachers. In addition, the study can help to raise public awareness about the importance of the Licensure Examination for Teachers and the role that it plays in ensuring that students are taught by qualified teachers. This can lead to greater support for teacher education programs, which can ultimately benefit students.

In the literature review, the researcher has found related studies such as the study of Frigillano et al., (2018) titled "Pre-Service

Teachers' Anxiety And Preparation Prior To Board Examination" which discussed anxiety levels in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) and the study of Binayao et al., (2020) titled "A Phenomenological Study of the Passers and Non-Passers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers" also discussed the lived experiences of the passers and non-passers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) of the Bukidnon State University education graduates from the main campus, external centers, and the Certificate of Teaching who took the professional education units. These studies only focus on the anxiety level of passers and non-passers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers; however, they did not focus on the preparation of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers. This means that the study specifically inquired on the Preparedness of Teacher Education Students for the Licensure Examination for Teachers are still less explored in the body of knowledge. These premises prompted me to propose this study.

Furthermore, the findings of the study can be disseminated through academic symposia and through research congresses where the relevant stakeholders can be the audience. This dissemination aims to enhance the preparation for the licensure examination for teachers by informing educational stakeholders of the latest findings, promoting evidence-based strategies, and fostering collaboration among educators to improve teaching practices and student outcomes.

Research Questions

In this study, convergent parallel mixed methods research was used in broadly examining the level of preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers among fourth-year teacher education students in KCAST. Specifically, this sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the Licensure Examination for Teachers?
2. What are the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of teacher education students in preparing for the Licensure Examination for Teachers?
3. To what extent do qualitative results corroborate with quantitative results?
4. On the basis of the findings, what intervention plan can be proposed?

Literature Review

Preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers

Preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in education refers to the readiness of teacher education candidates to successfully pass the exam required for obtaining their teaching license. This involves a strong grasp of subject content and pedagogical practices, as well as the ability to apply effective teaching strategies in diverse classroom settings. Furthermore, preparedness encompasses the development of strong study habits, time management skills, and emotional resilience to handle the pressures of exam preparation. Factors such as participation in review courses, access to mentoring, and supportive resources are crucial in enhancing students' readiness, ultimately increasing their likelihood of success on the exam and equipping them for effective teaching careers (Lucas, 2023).

Preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers is crucial, as it significantly influences students' confidence, commitment, and performance. A well-prepared teacher engages effectively with students, fostering a positive learning environment and addressing diverse needs. Research indicates that participation in review sessions, peer support, and a positive attitude toward learning enhance preparedness and commitment to the exam. Additionally, factors such as daily routines, self-assessment behaviors, and financial imitations affect education graduates' readiness. This highlights the need for comprehensive support mechanisms and resources to improve exam preparedness (Villaflora, 2023).

Hence, readiness for the licensure examination for teachers centered on the performance of teacher education graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) and its association with various student-related variables and challenges. The study highlighted the need to address challenges such as academic, psychological, and personal obstacles to improve board performance ratings. Additionally, it is important to consider student-related factors and challenges in preparing students for licensure examinations, emphasizing the significance of holistic support and interventions to enhance readiness and performance in such assessments (Tolete et al., 2024).

Moreover, Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) need to ensure that their students are adequately prepared for licensure exams to enable them to begin their careers as teachers. Pre-service teachers may need to put in extra effort to study and gain the necessary content and pedagogical knowledge to pass the exam and obtain their valid certificate of registration and professional license, by understanding the factors contributing to pre-service teachers' exam readiness, TEIs can support their students in achieving a passing score on the licensure exam and becoming licensed professionals (Aribon et al., 2023).

Also, preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers has shown various factors influencing readiness. Gabor's (2024) study highlighted that Education Graduates of PNC preparing for the LET engage in self-review practices due to financial constraints, emphasizing the importance of free LET reviews and quality review centers. These studies collectively underscore the importance of adequate preparation, support systems, and understanding of licensure policies in enhancing

educators' readiness for the licensure examination.

Personal Aspect

Personal aspect refers to the individual's unique characteristics, behaviors, thoughts, and emotions that define their identity and shape their interactions in various settings. Preparing for board examinations requires thorough attention. Several “personal factors” are recognized as influential, often assumed to be present and practiced, yet not always actively developed among students or examinees. These factors include their preparedness, personal motivation, study habits and skills, and time management (Briones et al., 2020).

Further, personal aspect is vital in preparing for licensure exams for teachers, as it directly affects study habits, stress management, and exam performance. Self-efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to succeed, builds confidence and persistence, leading to more efficient and focused study sessions. This mindset allows individuals to manage time well, concentrate on challenging topics, and retain information effectively. Additionally, self-efficacy helps individuals handle stress, ensuring they remain calm and resilient during exams. Overall, a strong personal foundation enhances both the preparation process and performance outcomes (Huang et al., 2018).

Hence, personal aspect encompasses factors such as eagerness to learn, willingness to take on challenging tasks, openness to feedback, and a commitment to self-improvement. It includes striving to achieve one's goals, pushing oneself to complete tasks, maintaining a positive attitude toward setbacks, and having confidence in one's note-taking abilities. These qualities foster resilience and a growth mindset, essential for academic success. Furthermore, the process of note-taking and reviewing plays a crucial role in learning, as it helps form new connections or reinforce existing ones between concepts. This active engagement with material leads to a deeper understanding and better assimilation of information (Lodge et al., 2018).

In connection, when reviewing for the LET (Licensure Examination for Teachers), it became evident through observation and feedback that a significant number of students struggled to maintain focus during study sessions, primarily due to engaging in multitasking behaviors, such as frequently checking their smartphones or browsing social media platforms. This trend poses a considerable challenge as it diverts their attention away from the critical review materials essential for success in the examination. Furthermore, the allure of social media platforms presents a constant temptation that can easily derail students from their preparation routines, leading to decreased productivity and retention of study materials (Junco, 2018).

Moreover, it provided tips to students on how to prepare for the board exams, including ways to enhance memory and retention capacity. One should have a strong desire to achieve and excel in any professional examination, as the personal aspect plays a crucial role in successful preparation. Setting practical targets is immensely helpful, as it allows students to maintain momentum and steadily work towards their goals. By setting daily, weekly, and monthly study targets, students can effectively manage their time, focus on areas where they are weaker, and gradually build a deeper understanding of the material. This approach, driven by personal motivation and self-discipline, ensures that goals are not only set but are also realistic and achievable, leading to better performance on the licensure examination for teachers (Khandhari, 2020).

Environmental Aspect

Environmental aspect is defined as the external conditions and influences that can significantly impact a student's study effectiveness and exam preparation. These include factors such as the physical study environment, availability of educational resources, social support systems, and access to modern technology. Additionally, family dynamics, financial stability, cultural expectations, and levels of community involvement significantly contribute to one's study success. Personal health, mental well-being, and the presence of positive role models are also essential components. Together, these interconnected factors help create a structured and supportive study environment, which is crucial for achieving optimal preparation and performance in high-stakes exams, such as the licensure examination for teachers (Garcia et al., 2018).

In connection, environmental aspect plays vital role in preparing for the licensure examination for teachers and significantly influence students' academic performance since it has a direct impact on their capacity to focus, access resources, and and keep a positive outlook. A supportive environment, characterized by a quiet study space, availability of learning materials, and strong social support, can significantly enhance focus and reduce anxiety, leading to more effective study sessions. A high-quality learning environment can help one institution improve the learning capabilities of the students (Robinson, 2021).

Moreover, environmental aspect is emphasized as a key factor in preparing for the licensure examination ensuring that the school provides adequate facilities and resources to foster a supportive learning environment. Such an environment supports students' focus and enhances their ability to study effectively. The availability of resources and proper infrastructure are essential for optimal preparation. By ensuring these conditions, schools can significantly contribute to student's success in the examination (Kandhari, 2020).

Hence, preparation for teachers' licensure examinations is influenced by both internal and external factors. It is suggested that review classrooms should be in a peaceful location, free from any disturbances, as noise can hinder reading, writing, and comprehension skills, affecting academic performance. A study was conducted to enhance the acoustic quality of open-plan study environments by examining the effects of various sound scenarios on students performing a typical academic task, “studying for an exam”. Therefore, it is recommended that review classrooms should be placed in a calm and distraction-free environment (Braat-Eggen et al., 2021).

Also, family support and encouragement can greatly motivate some students to achieve their goals, particularly during challenging periods of academic stress. On the other hand, not having this support can be a major obstacle that causes students to doubt their commitment to their aspirations, especially when faced with academic pressures and personal setbacks. It shows that the strength of the support provided is tied to the depth of the relationship between the student and their family. Having a strong social support system can help manage stress effectively, benefiting both mental and physical health and reducing emotional distress. When it comes to students, they require encouragement, motivation, and practical support in their everyday school lives. They also appreciate when their educational expectations are clearly expressed and regularly reinforced by those they trust (Schmid et al., 2021).

Instructional Aspect

Instructional aspect refers to items designed to aid students and teachers as a study tool, helping learners obtain information, skills, or perspectives, and enhancing cognitive abilities. Instructional materials are designed to be used by students and their teachers to support learning, helping learners acquire knowledge, skills, and perspectives, or enhance cognitive development. Instructional materials can be printed or non-printed and include textbooks, technology-based tools, other educational resources, and assessment materials (Shukla, 2018).

Moreover, instructional aspect is important for preparing for the licensure examination for teachers. It plays a crucial role in enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Research indicates that well-designed instructional materials significantly contribute to the preparedness of teacher education students, impacting their performance on licensure exams. These materials are critical tools for developing pedagogical skills and content knowledge necessary for effective teaching. It is essential to highlight that the integration of diverse instructional resources can improve candidates' understanding of complex educational concepts, thereby boosting their confidence and performance during examinations (Tekir et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the study highlights the crucial role of tailored study resources in preparing for the teachers' licensure examination. They emphasize that these materials significantly enhance student's performance by closely aligning with the exam's content and format. By focusing on the specific topics and question styles found in the LET, tailored review resources help students target their studies more effectively. This alignment ensures that students are better prepared for the types of questions they will encounter. Ultimately, using customized review materials can greatly increase the likelihood of success on the exam (Cayabas et al., 2023).

In addition, students taught using custom-made instructional materials demonstrated the highest level of achievement. Moreover, for these resources to be most effective, they need to be carefully created, chosen, organized, developed, and integrated into the curriculum. When preparing and selecting instructional materials, it's important to consider the breadth and depth of knowledge to enhance student learning. Furthermore, printed materials play a significant role in achieving success and passing the LET, as they support thorough preparation efforts (Binayao et al., 2020).

Also, enhancing the quality of educational materials is crucial for improving both teacher and student performance. The understanding that meeting the course objectives of the Teacher Education curriculum's general education, professional, and major components includes adequately covering the prescribed topics during the semester, utilizing instructional materials effectively, and employing appropriate assessment tools that have been proven to be reliable and valid with LET-measured competences, and the relevance of the course requirements and instructional tasks to the teacher education courses are all factors that contribute to passing the licensing exam (Delos Angeles, 2020).

Preparing for licensure examinations, like the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), is deeply influenced by personal, environmental, and instructional aspects. The personal aspect encompasses individual characteristics like motivation, study habits, and self-discipline, which are critical for effective exam preparation and performance. Environmental factors, such as a supportive study environment and social support systems, also play a significant role in enabling students to focus and manage stress effectively. Lastly, the instructional aspect highlights the importance of well-designed educational materials and tailored review resources, which enhance students' understanding and confidence, ultimately boosting their exam success.

These three aspect work synergistically to shape a students' readiness and ability to excel in high-stakes examinations.

Issues Faced by Teacher Education Students in Preparing for the Licensure Examination for Teachers

Within a comprehensive study, a significant hurdle when preparing for the licensure examination for teachers arose from a lack of commitment, which directly impacted students' ability to allocate consistent effort to their studies. Without strong motivation and focus, they often struggled to develop the discipline needed to thoroughly review key concepts and hone the skills required for success on the exam. Research showed that students with low levels of commitment tended to disengage from vital preparatory activities, such as attending review sessions or participating in collaborative learning with peers, which were essential for building confidence and mastery of the subject matter (Villaflores, 2023).

Moreover, according to another study, one significant challenge investigated in the preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers is poor time management, which severely hinders students' ability to allocate their study hours effectively while balancing competing responsibilities. This lack of effective time management often results in heightened stress levels and diminished study quality, ultimately detracting from their overall performance in exam preparation. Research indicates that many students struggle with

managing their time effectively, leading to chronic stress and compromised academic outcomes. For instance, numerous pre-service teachers reported a significant disparity between recommended study hours and the actual time they devoted to studying due to work commitments, which negatively affected their capacity to acquire the essential skills and knowledge needed for adequate preparation for the licensure examination (Burston, 2018).

In addition, another study examined the challenges encountered by teacher education students in the process of preparing for the teachers' licensure exam, highlighting a significant barrier: the lack of family support. This absence of encouragement and assistance can greatly impact students' motivation and confidence making it more difficult for them to navigate their studies and adequately prepare for the exam. Without a family understanding of the demands of teacher education programs, students may feel isolated and overwhelmed, leading to increased anxiety and diminished academic performance. Research indicates that students with low family support faced higher stress levels and struggled academically. Emotional support was particularly crucial, aiding in better study habits and reduced stress, while financial support often alleviated the need for part-time work, allowing more focus on preparation (Garcia et al., 2020).

Furthermore, a major obstacle in preparing for the teachers' licensure examination is the fear of failure that teacher education students often experience. This fear disrupts their ability to create effective study plans, leading to procrastination and avoidance of critical topics. Instead of thoroughly reviewing key concepts, students often become fixated on their anxiety, which undermines their overall readiness and the quality of their study efforts. Research indicates that students with high levels of fear of failure tend to be less engaged and less committed to essential preparatory activities. This anxiety creates mental blocks and prevents them from mastering the necessary concepts and skills for the exam (Nakhla, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher employed a mixed method design, which involves the integration of qualitative and quantitative elements to offer a more thorough understanding of the research problem. According to Halcomb et al. (2015), this integration is crucial for the rigor of mixed methods research, and it can occur at any stage of the research process. The term "mixing" is used to describe the process of merging qualitative and quantitative elements to deliver a more complete explanation of the research problem.

In the context of the study, a mixed-method approach was employed, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods to assess the preparedness of fourth-year teacher education students for the teachers' licensure examination. This approach enabled the researcher to acquire a more thorough and nuanced understanding of these students' preparedness for the exam. By combining the results obtained from different methods, researchers can potentially reveal new insights into students' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers that might be overlooked using a single-method approach.

The convergent parallel design, or convergent/triangulation design, entails the simultaneous execution of both quantitative and qualitative studies conducted during the same phase of the research process in this design. Both methods are given equal importance, allowing them to contribute equally to addressing the research problem. The design keeps the studies separate during the data collection and analysis, but then integrates or combines the results during the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

A convergent parallel mixed-method approach was selected as the research design for this study. Both quantitative and qualitative data were gathered simultaneously in this design, with equal weight given to both. In order to gauge students' readiness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), a survey was first given out followed by focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews to gather in-depth insights into their experiences and coping mechanisms for exam preparation. Both sets of data were analyzed independently, and the findings were merged to offer a thorough understanding of the students's preparations. This design is particularly suitable as it allows for the exploration of convergence between quantitative measures of preparedness and qualitative insights into students' perceptions and challenges.

Specifically, the quantitative component involved a descriptive approach. The descriptive approach is a study designed to accurately represent the participants. Simply put, it focuses on describing the individuals involved in the study and is used to outline the characteristics of the population or phenomenon being examined. These kinds of categorical schemes are also known as descriptive categories. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to enhance our understanding of preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers among fourth-year teacher education students. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Richardson, 2028).

Additionally, the fourth-year teacher education students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology were asked to participate in a survey that has been specially designed for them. The research study received responses from 89 individuals. Participants' collective responses were used to produce a number of problems. In order to do this, proper statistical methods, including frequency, weighted mean, and standard deviation was used. Following these procedures, data were displayed and examined using descriptive statistics.

In addition, phenomenological inquiry was employed in this study to enhance the qualitative framework. This approach facilitated the

exploration and understanding of the participants' experiences within their dynamic environment. Phenomenology emphasizes the shared essence of lived experiences among a specific group. Interviews are usually conducted with individuals who possess direct experience or knowledge of a particular event, situation, or experience. Additional data sources, such as documents and observations, may also be utilized (Creswell, 2013).

On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study adopted a phenomenological approach to examine students' preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). This method acknowledges the diverse, subjective experiences of students, allowing for a deeper understanding of their personal readiness for the exam. Through focus group discussions and one-on-one interviews, rich qualitative data were gathered, providing insights into the experiences and coping mechanism that shape students' preparation. The data were analyzed to identify key themes, offering a nuanced perspective on how students perceive and navigate their journey toward the LET preparation.

Participants

The participants were selected based on their ability to provide valuable insights, address the research questions, and enhance the understanding of the phenomenon being examined (Kuper, Lingard & Levinson, 2008). Specifically, the key participants in this research were the fourth-year teacher education students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology.

Quantitative Phase

The participants in this research comprised 4th-year teacher education students enrolled in Competency Skills Appraisal 1 under the ITED program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology during the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024. The selection of these students as respondents was deliberate, aligning with the study's focus on preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in the institution. Given the study's emphasis on fourth-year students who took education programs at the institution, it was deemed appropriate and valid to include fourth-year students specifically from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

The research was conducted among fourth-year teacher education students enrolled in the competency skills appraisal 1. The students enrolled comprise a total of 113 fourth-year students, consisting of 16 students in BEEd-Generalist, 30 students in BSEd-English, 34 students in BSEd-Filipino, and 33 students in BSEd-Mathematics. However, the study's sample size was determined by the statistician, encompassing 13 out of 16 from BEEd-Generalist. Similarly, the sample for BSEd-English included 24 out of 30, for BSEd-Filipino included 27 out of 34, and the sample for BSEd-Mathematics included 26 out of 33. In aggregate, the study sampled 89 students from the total pool of 113 students in the education program.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Mathematics	33	26	23.00%
Filipino	34	27	23.70%
BEEd-Generalist	16	13	11.15%
English	30	24	20.91%
Total	113	89	78.76%

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, subject selection in qualitative research was purposeful. In this phase, non-probability sampling specifically purposive sampling technique was utilized. Purposive sampling technique is a technique used in qualitative research to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis. Moreover, participants were selected who could best inform the research questions and enhance understanding of the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). The qualitative phase included 7 informants for the in-depth interview and another 7 participants for the focus group discussion. This conformed to the suggestion and recommendation of Creswell and Creswell (2018), which pointed out that a researcher may have between 10 to 50 participants as being sufficient in qualitative research depending on the type of research and research questions.

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	4th year
IDI-02	Female	4th year
IDI-03	Male	4th year
IDI-04	Female	4th year
IDI-05	Male	4th year
IDI-06	Female	4th year
IDI-07	Female	4th year
FGD-01	Male	4th year
FGD-02	Female	4th year
FGD-03	Female	4th year
FGD-04	Male	4th year

FGD-05	Female	4th year
FGD-06	Male	4th year
FGD-07	Female	4th year

Instrument

Research instruments refer to the devices used to collect data such as questionnaires, tests, structural interviews, and checklists. This convergent parallel mixed method study employed two research instruments- the survey questionnaire and the interview to gather the needed data from the participants (Seaman, 1991).

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative data needed for the investigation were provided by the instrument used during the quantitative phase of the study. A survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Natural et al. (2024) to collect quantitative data from the participants. The survey included a total of 15 items divided into three parts: personal aspect, environmental aspect, and instructional aspect, with each part containing 5 items. Participants responded on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 representing "infrequently" and 5 representing "always." Various means, descriptions, and interpretations were used to determine participants' level of preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers. The questionnaires were submitted for content validation and reliability testing. The Cronbach Alpha was 0.952, indicating that the instruments were reliable for measuring the variables.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand two questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey to explore deeper insights. It served as a compass for the in-depth interviews, guiding the conversation toward relevant topics. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, seven were purposively selected to undergo the IDI and another seven for the FGD. The interviews were suitable in gleaning insights, stories, personal narratives, experiences, opinions, and other useful information that could not be captured through numbers or quantitative data alone.

Procedure

The procedure for gathering the data includes a number of steps. Quantitative and qualitative data was gathered concurrently, nearly at the same time. Parallel mixed-method data collection techniques were used to compare data from diverse sources, modify the data for comparison, or answer various types of inquiries (Creswell & Clark, 2007).

Quantitative Phase

The researcher first request permission from the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology's office of the president to carry out this study in order to facilitate the collection of the required quantitative data. Additionally, the motivational orientation survey questionnaire, which was developed, was used in this study to gather quantitative data. In order to prevent participant mood changes during the quantitative data collection, the survey questionnaire was given to participants on the same day. The results were tallied, computed, and analyzed to corroborate the results of the qualitative data.

Qualitative Phase

Focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews with participants were part of the qualitative data collection to obtain information about the participants' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. The researcher asked the informants about their time availability for the in-person interviews before starting the focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews. The researcher also inquired about the location of the interviews. The researcher used a planned set of enabling questions during the one-on-one in-depth interview and also provided follow-up questions to ensure that all of the subjects' answers were covered. The researcher went into great detail during the interview about the individuals' ethical concerns.

Data Analysis

The tabulation of data and data analysis were completed immediately after all applicable data were obtained. The researcher employed thematic analysis to analyze the qualitative data, while specific statistical tools were utilized to analyze the data during the quantitative phase, ensuring a comprehensive examination of both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the study.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics, such as the mean, were used to determine the participants' average replies. Also, the standard deviation was used to assess the variability of the respondents' responses on the survey's preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers questionnaire, measuring how dispersed the data were from the mean (Creswell et al., 2017).

Qualitative Phase

However, participants' responses were recorded, arranged, and reduced to themes through a process of coding and condensing the

codes in qualitative data analysis. A narrative, a table, or a set of figures were used to present the data. The researcher immersed themselves in the rich, descriptive data during the analysis of the qualitative data, employing coding and categorization techniques to arrange the data. The objective was to create themes that could be utilized to describe the preparedness of fourth-year teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers. Thus, qualitative analysis was an iterative process that involved generating and refining themes repeatedly as well as reading and rereading the data to get a final analysis of the data to shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the fourth-year teacher education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

Social Value. This study sought to examine the readiness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers. To capture a diverse range of participant insights, which was the primary focus of the analysis, the data collection process was meticulously outlined. The findings were presented to both the participants and the public. Furthermore, the researcher upheld the social value of research by demonstrating a clear commitment to the accuracy of the convergent parallel mixed methods design utilized in the study.

Informed Consent. Study participants were provided with an informed consent form, which included details about the researcher's identity and affiliation, the study's purpose, its duration, and any incentives offered to participants, such as cash, gifts, or other items, in appreciation of their involvement. Due to the participants' privacy and secrecy, they were permitted to leave at any moment without giving a reason. The informed consent form (ICF) gave the participants the chance to read the information it contained, ask questions, and utilize their signature as a source of recommendations for the study.

The Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The core principle of ethical considerations was safeguarding the well-being of study participants to the extent that even researchers could not connect individuals with the information they provided and preventing the disclosure of a participant's identity to anyone except authorized personnel (Denzin et al., 2011).

When data was carefully published, there was a potential danger of harm in terms of social liabilities. As a result, the data of the study was kept secure and confidential to prevent incidents like these from happening. The researcher carefully committed the respondents' personal data from the study to address this issue. Respondents were not required to provide any personal information in the survey questions, such as name, email, and contact number.

In this study, the primary concern was the safety and security of the participants, all of whom were above the legal age of 18, ensuring no risk related to the involvement of minors. The conduct of the study adhered to the participants' preferred locations for gathering the needed data, guaranteeing their safety. In alignment with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), all data gathered were handled with strict confidentiality, and participants' rights to privacy were prioritized. Additionally, if participants felt any discomfort during the interview because of the sensitive nature of the topic under discussion, the researcher provided them the option to refrain from answering questions if they felt any psychological or emotional distress. If they were unable to discuss the requested data, they were free to withdraw from the study at any time.

Furthermore, as a gesture of goodwill, participants received small tokens to acknowledge their valuable contributions to the study. This expression of appreciation highlighted the researchers dedication to ethical research practices and respect for participant involvement. Such efforts reflect a commitment to fostering a positive research environment while ensuring the well-being of all participants.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. Any data that was identified by the participants during the study was kept strictly confidential. Individual names were replaced with codes. Participants were given the option of not disclosing their names on the survey form when responding to the questionnaire, and all responses were confidential and stored by the researcher in a closed filing cabinet for 3 years. Similarly, all names were removed from the records, ensuring that survey respondents could not be identified. Hard copies of the data, labeled with codes only, were securely stored and safeguarded.

Further, Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act, safeguards personal information handled within information and communication systems across both government and private sectors. It also established a National Privacy Commission to oversee its implementation and address related concerns. The Data Privacy Act of 2012, outlined in Section 2 of its general provisions, declared the State's commitment to safeguarding the fundamental human right to privacy in communication while promoting the free flow of information to foster innovation and growth. The State acknowledged the critical role of information and communications technology in nation-building and emphasized its responsibility to ensure the security and protection of personal information within government and private sector information systems. Any information that could potentially identify the participants, such as gender, ethnicity, or employment/location details, was carefully worded to maintain anonymity. Additionally, the data gathered was strictly used for the purposes of the study.

Justice. The study's participants were appropriate for the investigation because they were the ones that were selected. To avoid bias, the researcher adopted suitable sample strategies for both the quantitative and qualitative phases. Participants had the chance to read

information and ask questions to understand their part in the study throughout the informed consent process. The participants were also granted justice by contributing their time and knowledge to the completion of this study, in addition to receiving presents, goods, or anything else that was useful to their everyday lives. Justice was also upheld by maintaining the confidentiality of the data the researcher obtained, transcribing the collected data accurately and appropriately, and first sharing the findings with the participants.

Transparency. This study adhered to the ideals of transparency by completely informing the participants that the study concentrated on the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers. It was the researcher's responsibility to be just and fair in the conduct of this study. In addition, participants were presented with interview notes and transcribed documents for confirmation and approval. Therefore, the results of the study were shared with the respondents and participants.

Qualification of the Researchers. The researcher demonstrated reliability and credibility throughout the study, which focused on preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. As a third-year college student enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist program, the researcher conducted the study for personal growth and in alignment with research development goals.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher would ensure that there are existing and available resources needed for this institutional study. Online journals, periodicals, magazines, books, and unpublished dissertations were available for further understanding and references, which provided various literature and readings that supported the connotation of the variables used in the study. In this study, adequate facilities were provided, such as a laptop and cellphone, for the accuracy of collecting data from the participants during the study.

Community Involvement. During the initial presentation of this study, community leaders, faculty, and students were invited to the public forum, which was done through face-to-face interaction and presentations. This research generated awareness, and implications were given to the school administrators and instructors regarding the survey of technology proficiency among faculty members. The study was useful for the technical research committee, the conference managers, and journal publishers that helped disseminate the findings of this study aim to offer further insights and a more comprehensive understanding of teacher education students' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results of the study based on the analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data. The presentation of quantitative results started with the descriptive result which presents on the preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers among fourth-year teacher education students. Consequently, the presentation of the qualitative phase follows which included the thematic analysis of the lived experiences and coping mechanism shared regarding the preparedness of fourth-year teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers.

Level of Teacher Education Student's Preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers

Table 2 presents the level of fourth-year teacher education student's preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences of Technology in terms of their personal, environmental, and instructional aspect. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.31 with a description of Very High. This means that the fourth-year teacher education students always manifested their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Table 2. *Level of Teacher Education Student's Preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers*

No.	Items	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Personal Aspect			
1	Taking challenging tasks to learn new topics.	4.18	High
2	Taking responsible for additional learning given by the instructors during review.	4.31	Very High
3	Keeping track of areas for improvement in my studies.	4.24	High
4	Having a strong desire to achieve my goals and excel academically so that I can pass the LET exam.	4.49	Very High
5	Refining my techniques for the LET exam.	4.27	High
Category Mean		4.30	Very High
Environmental Aspect			
1	Focusing better in a classroom that is away from a noisy environment.	4.25	High
2	Being comfortable in a classroom with complete chairs and tables.	4.31	Very High
3	Focusing better in a classroom with enough lightning to read and answer test questions.	4.34	Very High
4	Using a room at home equipped with modern gadgets and internet access.	4.00	High

5	Refining my techniques for the LET exam.	4.27	High
Category Mean		4.30	Very High
Environmental Aspect			
1	Focusing better in a classroom that is away from a noisy environment.	4.25	High
2	Being comfortable in a classroom with complete chairs and tables.	4.31	Very High
3	Focusing better in a classroom with enough lighting to read and answer test questions.	4.34	Very High
4	Using a room at home equipped with modern gadgets and internet access.	4.00	High
5	willing to receive support and positive attitudes from my friends and family.	4.44	Very High
Category Mean		4.27	Very High
Instructional Aspect			
1	Using the review materials provided by our school	4.34	Very High
2	Directing my attention to the quality of printed materials to focus on my review.	4.20	High
3	Ensuring that the contents of printed materials are relevant in every subject area.	4.44	Very High
4	Assuring that the instructional materials include clear examples and explanations, presented effectively by instructors.	4.39	Very High
5	Assuring that the instructions given in the materials are concise and easy to follow.	4.40	High
Category Mean		4.36	Very High
Overall Mean		4.31	Very High

The study revealed high preparedness levels among fourth-year teacher education students across personal, environmental, and instructional aspects. The personal aspect had a category mean of 4.30, described as very high, indicating it is consistently manifested. The highest-rated item was having a strong desire to achieve goals and excel academically (4.49), while taking on challenging tasks to learn new topics rated lowest (4.18). In the environmental aspect, the category mean was 4.27, also very high. Receiving support from friends and family scored highest (4.44), whereas using a room with modern gadgets and internet access was rated lowest (4.00). For the instructional aspect, the category mean was 4.36, described as very high. Ensuring the relevance of printed materials in every subject area received the highest mean (4.44), while focusing on the quality of printed materials during reviews rated lowest (4.20). These results highlight the consistent preparedness of the students in all aspects, with minor variations across specific items.

Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanism of Teacher Education Students on their Preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers

There were eight essential themes drawn from the responses of the participants in the in-depth interview and focus discussion. Feeling not equipped with knowledge and skills resulting to acquiring of review materials, lacking of time management between social media and academic responsibilities, having difficulty in understanding text due to poor reading comprehension and vocabulary, experiencing challenges in achieving academic grade competency, attending regularly the review session and classes to enhance one's knowledge, engaging to various strategies for effective academic achievement, conditioning and preparing oneself, and obtaining multi-faceted forms of support from peers and family. It also discusses the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of teacher education students in terms of personal, environmental and instructional in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Table 3. *The Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanism of Teacher Education Students on their Preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code / Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Comprehensive Preparation Framework for LET Integrating Digital Study Aids, Compilation Techniques, and Resource Borrowing	Using app available on the Play Store called LET Reviewer - My LET as one of the resources to review for LET Searching videos on YouTube and Facebook that have content about LET questions Not relying solely on school questionnaires, but also joining online review centers for potential LET questions. Searching YouTube for video-based LET review materials. Looking for LET materials online that provides questions to review and memorize	Assessing Digital Study Aids	Lack of Knowledge and Skills Leads to Acquiring Review Materials	Cognitive Dissonance Theory

	Gathering CSA review materials for home study assessment Taking CSA questionnaires home for review and progress tracking Always value questionnaires as they help identify mistakes and enhance study effectiveness Keeping school-provided LET materials as study guides Conducting additional studies by reading library or borrowed books for LET preparation Expanding resources by borrowing materials from individuals who passed the LET Unsatisfied with stock knowledge, actively borrowing books from teachers or the library, particularly on major courses. Borrowing books from the library and acquaintances who passed the LET for comprehensive exam preparation	Compiling Study Materials from Review Session/CSA subjects Pedagogical Resource Borrowing		
Challenges in Balancing Social Media Engagement and studying for preparation for LET	Distracted by social media like Facebook and Instagram instead of studying for the LET Spending more time on Facebook and TikTok than studying for the LET Severely addicted to social media, easily shifting to Facebook and online games instead of studying for the LET Struggling to study due to heavy evening and weekend workloads Struggling with procrastination due to heavy lesson planning and tasks, impacting LET study time Struggling to find time for LET study due to on-the-job training and heavy workload	Devote More Time to Social Media Delay in Completing Task due to an Overwhelming Amount of Work	Struggling to Manage Time between Social Media and Academics	Self-Regulation Learning Theory
Effects of Low Reading Comprehension and Difficulty in Understanding High-Falutin Words in Studying for preparation for LET	Finding it hard to study for the LET due to training and heavy workload Poor reading comprehension often leads to mistakes and incorrect answers Spending too much time answering and guessing due to comprehension difficulties Frustrated and anxious about tricky questions, spending too much time answering Struggling to understand pretentious words in LET questions, making it hard to find answers Difficulty answering LET questions arises from confusing words, hindering comprehension	Reading Comprehension Difficulties Difficulty in Understanding High-Falutin Words Used in Texts	Difficulty Understanding Text due to Poor Comprehension and Vocabulary	Schema Theory
Impact of Experiencing the Burden of Academic Grades While Perceiving Competency as a Self-Competitor in Studying for Preparation for LET	Feeling pressured by grades can hinder LET preparation and achieving dreams Heavy emphasis on grades creates pressure and fear, affecting LET preparation Pressure from grades can disrupt study balance for LET preparation Fear of failing CSA adds pressure, affecting effective study Pressure to pass the CSA creates anxiety and disrupts effective study Anxiety about potential revalidation in the CSA exam hinders LET review concentration	Feeling Weighed Down by Academic Grades Academic Seeing Competency as Self-Competitor	Experiencing Challenges in Achieving Academic Grade Competency	Self-Determination Theory
Elevating LET Preparation Cultivating Academic Consistency and Accountability through Integrated Review/CSA Participation and Academic Responsibility	Consistently attending CSA sessions to stay on track with LET review Consistently attending CSA sessions to sharpen LET drill skills Consistently attending CSA sessions to review lessons and acquire essential LET techniques Consistently attending classes to build a strong	Participating Consistently in Review/CSA Academic	Regularly Attended Review Sessions and Classes to Enhance Knowledge	Self-Efficacy Theory

<p>Holistic Approach to Personal Development for effective studying in preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)</p>	<p>knowledge foundation for the LET Active class participation since the first year serves as a cornerstone for LET knowledge acquisition Committed to thorough study and consistent review to strengthen LET preparation Studying at 4 AM ensures a fresh mind and fewer distractions for better retention Scheduling morning study time enhances information absorption Setting a nighttime study timer helps focus and reduces distractions Setting a goal, like passing the LET, maintains focus and boosts motivation to study Motivating oneself to work hard to pass the LET Feeling motivated to study harder to pass the LET Playing chess and online games to relieve stress while studying for the LET Allocating time for writing to relieve stress and pressure Enjoying games, movies, or dramas to relieve LET study stress</p>	<p>Accountability Organizing Schedules for Study Establishing Goals for Inspiration Engaging in Hobbies and Interest</p>	<p>Engaging to Various Strategies for Effective Academic Achievement</p>	<p>Self-Determination Theory</p>
<p>Prioritize physical well-being with ample rest and balanced meals, while also seeking spiritual support through prayer for studying in LET preparation</p>	<p>Allowing rest to facilitate effective knowledge processing Maintaining good health to reduce LET preparation stress Balancing LET preparation stress by prioritizing meals and sleep Eating at appropriate times to support effective LET preparation Seeking guidance from God to stay focused while studying for the LET Surrendering to God to relieve pressure during LET preparation Talking to God for guidance in LET preparation</p>	<p>Ensuring Adequate Rest and Well-Balanced Meals Seek God's Intervention</p>	<p>Conditioning and Preparing Oneself</p>	<p>Self-Determination Theory</p>
<p>Imparting Kin and Non-Kin-Based Social Support</p>	<p>Mentors and friends provide guidance and knowledge to excel in the LET Mentors and classmates enhance LET preparation by offering strategies and facilitating idea exchange Friends and mentors offer invaluable support in LET preparation as study partners and guides on essential strategies Parents provide moral and financial support for CSA preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers Family serves as the primary support system during LET preparation Family motivates by reminding the importance of determination and resilience during LET preparation Family motivates belief in one's ability to prepare for the LET Feeling motivated to prepare for the LET through encouragement and support from parents</p>	<p>Colleague and Mentor Support Family Emotional Cohesion and Support</p>	<p>Obtaining Multi-Faceted Forms of Support from Peers and Family</p>	<p>Motivation Theory</p>

Lack of Knowledge and Skills Leads to Acquiring Review Materials. Taking into consideration the information and data gathered as shared by the participants through In-depth Interview and Focus Group Discussion, college students particularly the Fourth year Teacher Education Students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology express varying perspectives on their experiences in terms of their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. Majority of them shared that they're experience feeling not equipped with knowledge and skills resulting to acquisition of review materials.

Assessing Digital Study Aids. This is the first code on the first probed issue. Students commonly reported their experiences in preparing for the licensure examination for teachers. Most stated they are using digital study aids to develop the necessary competencies. They believe these tools are essential for success on the LET exam. This highlights the importance of technology in modern study practices. Many students feel more confident in their preparation with these resources.

During the interview, students highlighted online sources as the most accessible for securing review materials. Many preferred digital platforms because of their convenience and the available resources. Additionally, students emphasized the ease of use and flexibility that online sources offer. She conveyed that this shift towards digital learning tools has significantly improved study efficiency.

“Ako gina buhat kay mangita ko ug mga video sa youtube ug Facebook nga naay mga content about sa questions para sa LET human mag try kog answer tapos pag human sa video sa last naa man gd nay nakabutang nga mga correct answer so makabalo pod ka ug tam aba or mali imohang gina answer.” (IDI-01)

(I am searching for videos on YouTube and Facebook that contain content related to questions for the LET. After attempting to answer them, the correct answers are provided at the end of the video, allowing me to determine whether my answer is correct or incorrect.)

Similarly, FGD-01 collects questionnaires from the CSA to monitor her study progress through score assessments. This method helps her track her understanding and improvement over time. By regularly assessing her scores, she can identify strengths and areas needing more focus. Ultimately, these assessments provide a clear picture of her readiness for the exam. She articulated that:

“One of my ways no sa preparation sa LET kay gina uli nako sa balay ang mga questionnaire gikan sa CSA aside sa amoa na siya gina bayaran ug maka review ko ug balik kay ginabuhay nako siyang murag tally nga ma assess nako akoo kaugalingon kung naa bay progress akoo pag study base sa akoo mga score.” (FGD-01)

(To prepare for the LET, I have a method that involves bringing home the CSA questionnaires. I not only use the questionnaires that are provided to us but also purchase extra copies to review them again. I treat the questionnaires as a tally sheet to assess my progress in studying by tracking my scores.)

Additionally, FGD-05 did not disregard questionnaires, recognizing them as valuable tools for exam preparation. These questionnaires help identify mistakes, providing insights into areas needing improvement. By addressing these errors, she can focus her studying more effectively. It ensures a thorough understanding of the material, enhancing her readiness for the LET. She elaborated that:

“Sa akoo importante jud kaau ang mga materials nga gina provide during sa review or CSA namo kay sama sa gina ingon sa amoa review master nga dili jud dapat gina labay ang mga questionnaire kay isa na sa makatabang nga mabalik tan aw nako kung asa ko na mali para mas ma studyhan pa nako ug tarung.” (FGD-05).

(The materials provided during our review or CSA are of great importance to me. As our review master emphasizes, the questionnaires should never be discarded since they are one of the valuable tools that help me identify my mistakes. By studying and learning from them, I can improve my performance further.)

Furthermore, IDI-04 mentioned in the interview that they use the LET materials provided by the school as study guides at home. This approach helps them to prepare effectively for the LET exam. By doing so, they can better equip themselves with the necessary knowledge and skills. The materials serve as valuable resources throughout their study process. She stated that:

“Isa sa akoang ways sa preparation kay ang pag basa sa mga review materials nga gina provide sa school during CSA namo, dako jud siya ug tabang sa akoo labi na kay kalimtanon ko like dali rako makalimot sa lesson pag uli ug balay wala na. Maong gina keep jud nako ang mga materials nga ilang dina provide aron naa pod koy guide pag abot sa balay.” (IDI-04)

(I find it helpful to prepare for exams by reading the review materials provided by the school during our CSA sessions. I tend to forget things easily, especially when I am back at home. That is why I always make sure to keep the materials they provide so that I have a reference to guide me through my studies.)

Pedagogical Resource Borrowing. It is the third code of the issue that was probed. The participants shared that to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for LET, they engage in pedagogical resource borrowing. They find this method effective in supplementing their learning. By using borrowed resources, they can access a wider range of study materials. This practice allows them to deepen their understanding and enhance their preparation. Here are the collective reflections:

In the interview, it emerged that IDI-03 conducts additional studies by reading books borrowed from libraries and acquaintances to prepare for the LET. This method allows her to access a diverse range of materials and perspectives. By supplementing her primary study resources, she can deepen their understanding of key concepts. This strategy helps them to be more thoroughly prepared for the exam. She expressed that:

“Ang isa sa aking ginagawang paghahanda ay ang magsagawa ng karagdagang pag-aaral sa pamamagitan ng pagbabasa ng mga aklat na nagmula sa mga library o mga hiniram sa aking mga kakilala na siyang nakakatulong sa akin na mag handa sa LET.” (IDI-03)

(As part of my preparation for the LET, I conduct additional studies by reading books sourced from libraries or borrowed from

acquaintances.)

Furthermore, IDI-06 expands resources by borrowing materials from individuals who have successfully passed the LET exam. This approach helps to broaden his knowledge and gain insights from successful exam takers. By using these borrowed materials, he can access valuable study tips and strategies. This method supplements his study efforts and enhances their preparation. He articulated that:

“Para sa akoo mas nindot jud nga daghan kag kaila nga pwede nimo hirman sa mga books ug review materials pareha nako dili ko mag salig lang sa isa ka resources or ka ng gina hatag sa amoa during CSA naga hiram jud ko sa mga na una sa akoo kadtong mga nakapasar na daghan man kaau na sila ug mga materials so mao ako gina hiram pod para mas wide akoo knowledge.” (IDI-06)

(For me, it is better to have many acquaintances from whom you can borrow books and review materials. Like me, I do not rely on just one resource or what is provided to us during CSA. I also borrow from those who have gone before me, as they have a lot of materials. That is why I borrow from them as well, to broaden my knowledge.)

Similarly, FGD-02 is not content with relying solely on stock knowledge; instead, she actively borrow books from teachers or the library, particularly those related to their major courses. She expresses a proactive approach to supplementing her learning through external resources. By borrowing books from knowledgeable sources, she aims to deepen their understanding and expand their knowledge base, expressing:

“Naga hiram jud kog books gikan sa Library labi na sa amoa major pareha sa gina ingon sa amoa dapat dili me contented dapat kung unsa lang ang amoa mga stock knowledge maong naga pangita or hiram jud kog mga books and materials from teachers nga kaila ug kung kinsa pa dira.” (FGD- 02)

(I often borrow books from the library, especially for our major subjects. As our teachers tell us, we should not be content with just our existing knowledge. That is why I actively seek out or borrow books and materials from teachers and other acquaintances.)

Additionally, FGD-03 feels ill-equipped for the LET and therefore borrows books from various sources such as the library, acquaintances, and individuals who have successfully passed the exam. This borrowing practice is seen as essential for supplementing their preparation and enhancing their knowledge base. By accessing diverse resources, she aim to fill gaps in their understanding and gain valuable insights into exam strategies. She elaborated that:

“Dapat unlimited jud akoo knowledge para sa LET so dili man nako kaya mag palit ug mga books pero naa may library didto ko naga hiram para naa koy basahon or ka ng mga kaila nako labi kadtong mga naka pasar na sa LET gina hiram nako na ilaha kay para ma dagdagan pa akoo knowledge.” (FGD- 03)

(I need to have access to unlimited knowledge for the LET exam, but I cannot afford to buy books. Fortunately, I borrow books and materials from the library and also from acquaintances who have passed the LET exam. By borrowing their materials, I can further increase my knowledge and prepare better for the exam.)

Struggling to Manage Time between Social Media and Academics. This is the second essential theme drawn from the responses of participants from in-depth interview and focus group discussion. When the core ideas and categories were analyzed and synthesized, it highlights how students struggle to balance their academic responsibilities with social media, often resulting in poor time management skills affecting their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Devote More Time to Social Media. This is the first code of the issue that was probed. The participants shared that they face significant challenges in balancing their studies for the licensure examination for teachers, frequently finding themselves spending excessive time on social media. This struggle disrupts their study schedules and concentration levels, making it increasingly difficult to maintain effective focus.

During the interview, IDI-04 mentioned that she is frequently distracted by social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, instead of focusing on her studies for the LET exam. This distraction is affecting her ability to concentrate and prepare for the exam, which is impacting her productivity and readiness for the licensure examination for teachers. The attraction to social media is creating a big problem in her study routine. She stated that:

“Kabalo ko nga common siya dili lang sa akoo since surrounded man ta sa technology always jud nga naga kuan sa akoo ang social media, FB, Instagram ug uban pa so tungod ana is ma re-direct ang akoo ttime instead mag study ka mag scroll-scroll nalang ko sa facebook tan aw ug tiktok shared ug memes mas daghan pakog na a lot nga time sa social media kaysa mag study.” (IDI-04)

(I know it is common, not just for me, since we are surrounded by technology. I am always tempted by social media, such as Facebook, Instagram, and others. Because of that, my time gets redirected. Instead of studying, I end up simply scrolling through Facebook, watching TikTok, or sharing memes. I spend more time on social media than studying.)

Similarly, FGD-06 is experiencing the challenge of choosing to spend time scrolling through social media and watching TikTok videos instead of studying for the licensure examination for teachers. This habit significantly hinders his ability to dedicate sufficient time to exam preparation. Consequently, his study routine is disrupted, affecting his overall focus and productivity. He stated that:

“Kani jud social media ayy mo abot jud ko sa time nga nag Facebook ra di ay ko imbis mag study labi na kay naa nay Tiktok na ig nalang jud ko ug sayaw-sayaw sa tiktok dako jud kaaun nako ng pag sulay mas gi una pa nakong hing ana kaysa mag study.”(FGD-06)

(I find myself getting distracted by social media, particularly Facebook and TikTok, instead of studying. TikTok is especially tempting for me because I enjoy dancing on the platform. Unfortunately, this often takes priority over my studies.)

In addition, IDI-05 is also severely addicted to social media, spending all his time on Facebook and playing online games instead of studying for the LET. This addiction significantly hampers his ability to focus on exam preparation. The constant engagement with online platforms takes away valuable study time. Consequently, his productivity and readiness for the licensure examination for teachers are adversely affected. He stated that:

“Grabe jud ang kuan nako sa social media ma balhin jud akoo attention sa Facebook mag scroll-scroll ug mag sige kog chat-chat sa messenger usahay mag dula nalang pod ko ug online games mahurot nalang akoo time sa social media wala nako naka study.” (IDI-05)

(I have a serious addiction to social media. My attention is easily diverted to Facebook, where I spend time scrolling through the feed and chatting on Messenger. Sometimes, I get caught up playing online games and before I realize it, I end up wasting all my time without studying for the LET exam.)

Delay in Completing Task due to an Overwhelming Amount of Work. This is the second code of the issue probed. Participants from both in-depth interviews and focus group discussions expressed that their overwhelming workload is making it increasingly difficult for them to study in prepare for the licensure examination for teachers. The sheer volume of tasks they must manage leaves them with little time and energy to focus on their exam preparation. As a result, their ability to effectively study and be adequately prepared for the licensure examination is significantly compromised.

IDI-06 shared during the interview that he is struggling to keep up with his studies for the licensure examination for teachers due to a heavy workload and numerous classes. His busy schedule leaves him with little time or energy to focus on exam preparation, making it difficult to study effectively. The constant demands on his time and attention are impacting his ability to prepare thoroughly for the exam. He expressed concern about how these challenges are affecting his overall readiness. As a result, he finds it hard to concentrate and perform well in his studies. He mentioned that:

“The challenges I face kay matapulan ko tungod sa ka daghan na nako ug buhatunon because we are ongoing on our field study that time and then class during the classes hours in the night and also weekend so ang buhatunon nag tapok na ma wad an jud ko ug gana dili na nako buhaton dili na pod ko ka study.” (IDI-06)

(I often feel overwhelmed due to the numerous tasks I have to complete. At the time, we were conducting a field study, and attending classes in the evenings and even on weekends, which left me with a pile of work. As a result, I lose motivation and end up not completing any of them. This makes it hard for me to focus on my studies for LET as well.)

Similarly, according to FGD-04, the heavy workload of creating lesson plans and completing other tasks is causing her to struggle with procrastination. This issue significantly affects her preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The constant pressure of work leaves her with little motivation to study. As a result, her focus and productivity suffer. She stated that:

“Ika-duha kay naga procrastinate ko tungod sa ka daghan namo ug buhatunon gama lesson plan ug unsa pa ang task dira unya kailangan pa nako mag study kay naa me review or CSA wala na jud wala nako kasabot sa akoo unahon hing ana.” (FGD-04)

(I procrastinate because we have so many tasks, such as making lesson plans and completing other assignments. Furthermore, I still need to study for reviews or CSA. I am struggling to determine which task I should prioritize first.)

Moreover, FGD-07 mentioned during the interview that she is having difficulty finding time to study for the licensure examination for teachers. This is primarily due to her on-the-job training and heavy workload. The demands of her training and work leave her with little time to dedicate to study. Consequently, her ability to study effectively is significantly impacted. She stated that:

“Ako pod naga procrastinate ko mo abot jud ko sa ana nga part sa akoo kinabuhi labi na kay naga undergo me sa on the job training namo grabi jud dili lalim whole week days buntag duty ko pagka gabii mga lesson nga kailangan namo andamon para ugma hing ana tapos weekend review murag malibog bitaw ko tungod sa ka daghan dili na nako ma singit ang mag review.” (FGD-07)

(I also struggle with procrastination, particularly during this time when we are undergoing on-the-job training. It is really tough and not easy at all. I have morning duties all week long, and at night, I need to prepare lesson plans for the next day. Then on weekends, there is review, and I feel overwhelmed because of the many tasks. I cannot find time to fit in studying for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).)

Difficulty Understanding Text due to Poor Comprehension and Vocabulary. Another essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is their struggles to understand text due to poor reading comprehension and limited vocabulary affecting preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The participants noted that their responses to questions were influenced by their struggles with reading comprehension and limited vocabulary.

Reading Comprehension Difficulties. This is the first code of the third probed issue. Participants shared that they experience significant difficulty understanding questions for the licensure examination for teachers. Their low reading comprehension skills are adversely affecting their ability to prepare effectively. This challenge hinders their understanding of exam materials and reduces their confidence.

IDI-01 stated during the interview that she faces significant challenges due to her low reading comprehension and analysis skills. These difficulties make it hard for her to thoroughly understand the questions in the licensure examination for teachers' review. As a result, her ability to effectively prepare for the exam is compromised. The struggle with comprehending and analyzing exam materials affects her confidence. As expressed by IDI-01:

"Para sa akong ang significant challenges na akoang na face during sa review or CSA namo kay low kog reading comprehension ug analyzation mao gyud na ang ka ng challenges no ka ng pagbasa bitaw nako sa questions tuara wa nako kasabot." (IDI-01)

(For me, the significant challenges I faced during my review or CSA were my low reading comprehension and analysis skills. That was truly the main difficulty I encountered; I struggled to thoroughly understand the questions.)

Moreover, during the interview, FGD-03 expressed that facing struggles with poor reading comprehension often results in making mistakes and providing incorrect answers in drills. This issue significantly affects their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The inability to fully understand the material leads to errors and a lack of confidence. Consequently, their overall readiness for the exam is compromised. She mentioned that:

"Labaw na sa akong nga hina ug comprehension lisud jud kaayo kay dili jud ko kasabot sa akong gibasa usahay labi na sa nga question tapos pag mamali ka ug sabot mali na pod imoha answer kay wala man ko kasabot sa question maong medyu struggle jud ko dira nga part." (FGD-03)

(For me, having weak comprehension skills is particularly challenging because there are times when I do not understand what I am reading, especially when it comes to questions. Consequently, if I misunderstand or misinterpret, my answer becomes incorrect because I did not grasp the question properly. Therefore, I really struggle with that aspect.)

Furthermore, IDI-07 expressed during her interview that spending an excessive amount of time answering drills during review, and resorting to guessing due to difficulties in comprehension, can adversely affect preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The inability to comprehend questions thoroughly forces her to guess, which undermines her readiness for the exam. She mentioned that:

"Lisud pod sama sa akong nga low kog reading comprehension dili jud nako na ikaila kay mo abot pa jud kog kapila nako basahon ang questions bago nako masabtan unya wala na samot maka dugay sa akong time pag answer unya dili jud pa jud sure kay syempre naglisud kog sabot uban kay mag tagna-tagana nalang ko." (IDI-07)

(It is challenging for me to have low reading comprehension. I cannot deny it because I often need to read the questions several times before understanding them, which consumes more of my time to answer. Yet, even after that effort, I am still not entirely confident because I frequently resort to guessing due to my struggle with understanding.)

Difficulty in Understanding High-Falutin Words Used in Texts. It is the second code of the issue probed. Participants shared that they experience significant difficulty understanding the highfalutin words used in the texts for licensure examination for teachers review questions. This challenge hinders their ability to comprehend and accurately respond to exam questions, affecting their overall performance.

During the interview, IDI-07 shared that she experiences frustration and anxiety when encountering questions containing tricky words. This difficulty leads to spending excessive time answering drills during her review sessions. Consequently, her preparation for the licensure examination for teachers is adversely affected. The struggle with understanding complex vocabulary undermines her efficiency. She stated that:

"Ang uban man gud mga questions same atong sa drills namo during review maglisud kog sabot kay naay mga words nga tricky kaau siya ba libugon bitaw jud kag maayo tapos ako nga hina kog reading comprehension kailangan pa jud nako siya balik-balikon ug basa." (IDI-07)

(Some questions are similar to those in our review drills, making it difficult for me to understand because there are words that are very tricky and confusing, and I need to go over them repeatedly due to my poor reading comprehension.)

Additionally, FGD-06 said during the interview that she finds it challenging to understand the pretentious words used in LET questions during the review. This difficulty makes it hard for her to find the correct answers. The complex vocabulary hinders her comprehension and slows down her progress. As a result, her confidence and efficiency in preparing for the exam are adversely affected. She mentioned that:

"Pareha sa akong nga hina ug comprehension syempre maglisud jud kog sabot inig basa pa lang nako unya naa pa jud uban nga mga words nga gigamit sa mga sample questions for LET during sa CSA kay halos dili ko kasabot as in naglisud jud ko maong ma dugay ko ug human answer kay wala man ko kasabot sa mga meaning ato nga words." (FGD-06)

(Like me, with low comprehension skills, I naturally struggle to understand as soon as I start reading. Furthermore, there are additional words used in the sample questions for the LET during the CSA that I find particularly challenging to comprehend. This difficulty prolongs my answering process as I grapple with understanding the meanings of those words.)

Furthermore, FGD-05 expressed during the interview that she encountered significant difficulties when answering questions for the licensure examination for teachers during the review sessions. She explained that the challenge primarily stemmed from the confusing and sometimes ambiguous wording of the exam questions. The use of complex vocabulary, unfamiliar terms, and tricky phrasing often made it hard for her to grasp what the questions were asking fully. As a result, she found herself second-guessing her understanding of the material, which negatively impacted her ability to select the correct answers confidently. She emphasized that this challenge created additional stress and anxiety, further affecting her performance during the review. She mentioned that:

“Nakabantay ko sa mga questions for LET during sa amoa CSA kay llibugon jud ka pag ayu para sa ako no lisud jud kay dili man ko kasabot sa uban words nga gigamit maong mag lisud pod kog comprehend sa questions unya pag mag lisud mao ng kailangan nako balikon kapila ug basa ang questions.” (FGD-05)

(I noticed during our CSA sessions that preparing for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) can be quite perplexing. It is easy to become confused while studying, especially for me, as I find it challenging to understand some of the terminology used. As a result, I also struggle to comprehend the questions, and I have to return and read them several times.)

Experiencing Challenges in Achieving Academic Grade Competency. Another theme drawn from the responses of the participants is their challenges in achieving academic grade competency. These difficulties create considerable pressure as they strive to meet the required academic standards. This pressure, in turn, adversely affects their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. Balancing academic demands with exam preparation becomes increasingly difficult, leading to stress and reduced effectiveness in their study.

Feeling Weighed Down by Academic Grades. This is the first code of the third probed issue. The participants shared that they experienced feeling weighed down by academic grades which affected how they studied in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The constant stress of meeting academic expectations detracts from their focus and efficiency in their review.

Feeling pressured by grades can act as a significant barrier to studying for the LET. This pressure often diverts focus away from effective exam preparation. The constant worry about maintaining high academic standards can lead to stress and burnout. Consequently, students may find it challenging to concentrate and absorb the material needed for the licensure examination. As expressed by IDI-03:

“Siguro dili me nila e pressure about sa amoa grades kay mao jud may reason nganong mao nay maging barrier nga makab-ot akong pangandoy.” (IDI-03)

(Perhaps they do not pressure us about our grades because that is the reason why it becomes a barrier to achieving my dream of passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).)

Moreover, As expressed by IDI-04, the heavy emphasis on the grading system leads to significant pressure and a fear of failure. This stress directly impacts how she studies in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The constant worry about grades creates a mental barrier that hinders effective learning. Consequently, her focus and efficiency during study sessions are compromised. She mentioned that:

“Sa karon naga put sila ug emphasis sa grading system so na pressured nga natuok kay nahadlok ma fail hing-ana man gud ang system karon so ang akua lang ma ingon nga dili sila mag put ug too much pressure sila to the point nga gina push na sa namo ang among kaugalingon mag sige ug study na wala nako na nalipay at the end makalimtan japon nako akua gipang studyhan during sa CSA kay lahi raman gud ang learnings kung nalipay or na enjoy kay magpabilin jud na sa huna-huna biskan kapila pa na siya balikon or sa kadugayon.” (IDI-04)

(At present, they are emphasizing the grading system so much that it feels suffocating, and there is a fear of failure. This type of system is daunting. My standpoint is that they should not place too much pressure on us to the extent that we lose ourselves, constantly studying without finding joy. In the end, I still forget what I have studied during the CSA because learning is different when it is enjoyable and remains in your mind, even if you have to revisit it many times or spend a long time on it.)

Furthermore, being pressured by grades can disrupt the balance when studying for the licensure examination for teachers. IDI-02 expressed during her interview that this pressure creates a significant challenge in maintaining a steady study routine. The constant concern about academic performance detracts from her ability to focus on her review. She mentioned that:

“Sana they don’t put too much pressure sa amoa nga students nga naga review labi na sa grades kay lahi-lahi man gud para sa akua dili siya helpful kay mawala ko sa akoang balance.” (IDI-02)

(I hope they do not place too much pressure on us students who are reviewing, especially regarding grades, because for me, it is not helpful. It disrupts my balance.)

Academic Seeing Competency as Self-Competitor. It is the second code of the issue that was probed. Participants shared that they view academic competency as a personal challenge or competition with themselves. This mindset affects their studying in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The constant self-imposed pressure to excel academically can lead to increased stress and anxiety. Consequently, this internal competition detracts from their focus and efficiency in their review.

The participants expressed that their fear of failing the CSA adds significant pressure during review sessions. This anxiety creates a stressful environment that impedes their ability to study effectively. The constant worry about potential failure distracts from productive learning. As a result, their focus and efficiency during their review are compromised. As expressed by FGD-05:

“Lahi-lahi man gud ug facing ang tao sa pag ka ng pag process sa mga lecture or sa mga lesson kailangan pa jud nako balik-balikon ug basa kay lisud jud siya para sa akua ang mga drills unya dili ko bright nga dali ra makasabot inig review tapos sabayan pa jud ug kahadlok nga mabagsak sa CSA maong ma apektahan jud akua pag review.” (FGD-05)

(Every individual encounters unique challenges when processing lectures or lessons. I often find myself needing to revisit material because the drills are particularly difficult. I do not grasp concepts quickly during reviews, and the fear of failing the CSA only adds to the pressure, significantly impacting my ability to review effectively.)

Moreover, FGD-06 expressed during the interview that the pressure to pass the competency skills appraisal causes considerable anxiety, which severely affects her ability to study effectively for the licensure examination for teachers. She explained that the overwhelming stress of meeting the required standards creates a mental burden, making it difficult for her to focus on the material. The constant worry about failing to meet expectations disrupts her concentration, leading to a less productive study routine. This heightened anxiety not only affects her confidence but also limits her ability to stay motivated, further diminishing the effectiveness of her study sessions. She stated that:

“In terms sa CSA naa me gina aim nga dapat pasaron maong inig mag answer nami sa drills makulbaan jud ko kay isa lisud jud ang mga questions labi na sa kadtong post-test namo unya nawala na tanan gi studyhan tungod sa ka pressure nga dili makapasas sa CSA kay lahi ra jud ng mag review nga hapsay ang huna-huna.” (FGD-06)

(In terms of the CSA, our goal is to pass it. So when we answer drills, I become nervous because the questions are difficult, especially during the post-test, where everything we studied seems to vanish due to the pressure of not passing the CSA. It is a completely different experience when reviewing with a clear mind.)

Furthermore, FGD-04 expressed that the anxiety of potentially facing revalidation makes it even more challenging to concentrate on reviewing for the licensure examination for teachers. The fear of having to undergo revalidation adds significant stress to the preparation process. This heightened anxiety disrupts focus and impairs the ability to study effectively. She mentioned that:

“Base sa CSA namo dili gud sayon mag study or review unya sabayan ug kahadlok nga mabagsak kay sa CSA man gud hadlok nga ma revalida maong lisud kaau siya e focus sa pag review kay pressure kaau instead nga mka concentrate ug answer sa mga drills nga dili malimtan ang mga concept na kailangan for LET wala na kay nahadlok naman.” (FGD- 04)

(Studying or reviewing based on our CSA is not easy, especially with the added fear of failing due to its challenging nature. The pressure makes it difficult to focus on reviewing, hindering concentration on answering the drills and recalling the necessary concepts for the LET due to fear.)

Regularly Attended Review Sessions and Classes to Enhance Knowledge. The coping mechanism of the fourth-year teacher education students in accordance with their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers is being affected based on the similar responses given by the participants. Based on the information given the participants, it is claimed that because of the experience regarding their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers they attend regularly to the review sessions and classes to enhance one’s knowledge.

Participating Consistently in Review/CSA. This is the first code of the probed issue. Consistently participating in review sessions and CSA to enhance studying and prepare for the licensure examination for teachers. According to the participants, by participating consistently in a review/ competency skills appraisal they can acquired more knowledge, concepts, and skills that help them in studying for preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Likewise, IDI-01 consistently attends competency appraisal skills sessions to stay on track with her LET review. This commitment helps her avoid falling behind in her preparation for the licensure examination. Regular attendance ensures she remains updated and aligned with the required competencies. By participating actively in these sessions, she maintains a structured study routine. She expressed that:

“Sa part sa akua preparation dili jud ko naga absent basta CSA namo like big deal jud kaau na sya sa akua kay dako kaau ug impact ug dili ko mka attend kay ma left behind ko sa review namo.” (IDI- 01)

(In my preparation, I make sure not to miss any CSA sessions. It is crucial to me because it significantly influences my progress, and missing one could set me back in my review.)

Additionally, by consistently attending competency skills appraisal sessions, IDI-07 works to refine her skills in answering drills. These sessions are instrumental in her preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. Regular participation helps her stay sharp and effectively practice the types of questions she will encounter. This focused approach is essential for improving her performance and readiness for the licensure examination for teachers. She states that:

“Always jud ko naga attend sa CSA namo kay isa na siya ang dakong tabang sa preparation nako sa LET. Labi na sa amoa drills mahasa jud kog maau sa pag answer nga dapat maka pasar ko sa drills kay naa man pod gud consequence ug dili ma abot ang score sa passing.” (IDI-07)

(I consistently attend our CSA sessions because they greatly assist me in preparing for the LET. Particularly during our drills, they significantly improve my ability to answer effectively, which is crucial for passing, as failing to meet the passing score carries consequences.)

Furthermore, DI-05 articulated that regularly participating in CSA sessions is crucial for reviewing and solidifying lessons. These sessions provide him with essential techniques and concepts necessary for the licensure examination for teachers. By actively engaging in these reviews, he reinforces his understanding of key material. This consistent practice helps him grasp important concepts more effectively. He remarked:

“Isa nga way of preparation nako kay ang pag attend ug CSA namo nga subject although required siya pero dako jud siyang tabang no para sa akua kay dira ma refresh ang mga topics namo gikan first-year to third-year. Makatuon kog mga techniques and concepts maong ginahatg jud nako ang best, tarungon nako ug answer ang questions ug maminaw kog tarung sa amoa review master.” (IDI-05)

(One of my methods of preparation is attending our CSA sessions, even though they are mandatory. However, they are truly beneficial because they review topics from first-year to third-year. I learn various techniques and concepts during these sessions, enabling me to perform at my best, answer questions accurately, and attentively listen to our review master.)

Academic Accountability. This is the second code of the probed issue. The participants emphasize the sense of responsibility or accountability in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. They accomplished their tasks and complied with the requirements that were expected of them as students. They all yearned to pass and be successful in LET and extended efforts in the preparations.

IDI-07 mentions that regularly attending classes is essential for building a solid foundation of knowledge for the licensure examination for teachers. This consistent attendance ensures that he acquires a thorough understanding of the key concepts and material needed for the exam. By actively participating in these classes, he strengthens his grasp of important topics. She elaborated:

“Kuan aside sa CSA kay mo sulod jud kag klase regularly kay dira gina tudlo ang mga subject nga part sa examination sa Let by that daghan kog matun an nga mahimong foundation sa akua mga knowledge inig mag take nako ug Licensure Examination puhon.” (IDI-07)

(In addition to the CSA, I attend classes regularly as they cover subjects essential for the LET exam. This helps me acquire a strong foundation of knowledge that will support me when I take the Licensure Examination in the future.)

Similarly, FGD-05's pursuit of academic excellence and a thorough understanding of lessons from the first to the third year significantly contribute to his preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. His dedication to mastering each subject lays a strong foundation for the exam. This comprehensive approach ensures that he retains crucial knowledge and skills. By consistently aiming for excellence, he enhances his readiness for the licensure examination. He states that:

“So importante pod no as preparation nako for LET ang mag tarung sa pag skwela like ug naay mga projects ug tasks kay buhaton nako siya with best ug ang mga lesson namo kay tun an jud nako na ka ng gina saulo nako ba kay isa man gud na sa makatabang nako puhon ug mag take nako ug LET kay naa koy mga mahinumduman sa akua mga lesson gikan sa first to third year nako.” (FGD- 05)

(So, it is also important for me, as preparation for the LET, to excel in my studies, complete projects and tasks with excellence, and thoroughly understand our lessons. I make sure to do my best because it will greatly help me when I take the LET, as I have memories of my lessons from my first to third year.)

In addition, IDI-06 has actively participated in class discussions since the first year, which serves as the cornerstone of his knowledge acquisition for the licensure examination for teachers. His engagement in discussions helps solidify his understanding of key concepts. This active involvement ensures he retains and comprehends crucial information. By contributing to and learning from class dialogues, he strengthens his preparation for the exam. He noted:

“Dili lang pod ang pag sulod sa review session no isa pod ang pag tinarung sa sulod sa klase sinugdanan pa jud kay gikan first year hangtod karon kadtong mga lesson nga gina tackled mao nay soul sa akua knowledge nga dapat dili nako kalimtan mao nay pinaka basic nga dapat dala-dala nako inig mag take nako LET.” (IDI-06)

(Not only do I attend review sessions, but I also study diligently in class from the beginning, starting from the first year until now. The lessons covered in class serve as the foundation of my knowledge, which I should not forget. These are the fundamental basics that I

should carry with me when I take the LET.)

Furthermore, FGD-01 is committed to thorough study from the outset, consistently reviewing lessons to strengthen her knowledge in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. This dedication to regular study ensures that she retains and understands key concepts. By continually revisiting and reinforcing his lessons, he builds a solid foundation of knowledge. She remarked:

“At the very beginning pa lang first year pa lang gina look forward na jud nako nga consistent bitaw ko sa akua pag studies pareha anang ting exam naga study jud ko ug maau para mo excel ba academically kay isa man gud na nga naga tuo ko nga makatabang sa akua labi na karon sa preparation sa LET kay kung una pa lang sa mga lesson gina studyhan nimo lig-on ang imoha knowledge sa mga basic concepts ug throughout sa Year nako ug balik-balik ug tuon ana wala jud nako nalimtan.” (FGD-01)

(Right from the very beginning, even in my first year, I have always been committed to studying consistently. I make sure to study well for exams to excel academically because I believe it will benefit me, especially now in preparing for the LET. By studying the lessons thoroughly from the start, I strengthen my knowledge of basic concepts. Throughout the years, I have revisited and studied them repeatedly, so I have not forgotten.)

Engaging to Various Strategies for Effective Academic Achievement. The coping strategies of the fourth-year teacher education students, aligned with their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers, appear to be influenced by similar responses from the participants. According to the information shared by the participants, utilizing various strategies for effective academic achievement eased their test anxieties because of their ability to work well independently on the knowledge of the test content overcoming challenges during preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Organizing Schedules for Study. The first code of the probed issue. As per the participants' perspectives, organizing a study schedule is a vital component of preparing for the licensure examination for teachers. A well-structured schedule helps them stay focused and manage their time effectively. It also allows them to identify areas that need improvement and allocate sufficient time to address these weaknesses.

In line with this, IDI-02 shares that being specific with study time, such as around 4 am, ensures a fresh mind and fewer distractions. This early morning schedule makes it easier for the brain to absorb information needed for the licensure examination for teachers. The quiet and calm environment at this time is ideal for focused studying. Additionally, this routine helps establish a consistent study habit. She stated that:

“Dapat specific ka sa imohang time pag study ako kay naga study ko ug kadlawon 4 am kay fresh jud kaau akua utok ana wala pa kaau samok kay kadlawon pa man so bali ang imo gi studyhan mao nay mo sulod una sa imoha brain.” (IDI-02)

(You should be specific about your study time. For me, I study early at 4 am because my mind is fresh and there are fewer distractions at that time. So, whatever you study goes straight into your brain first thing.)

Moreover, FGD-04 highlights the crucial role of scheduling study sessions in the early morning to maximize information retention for the licensure examination for teachers. This strategy leverages the brain's peak performance period, enhancing concentration and memory. By dedicating morning hours to studying, she can absorb the necessary material more effectively. She remarked that:

“Pag mata bitaw nimo kadlawon kay ka ng mao jud to ang mo sulod sa imo huna-huna ba ka ng foam ban ga wala pay tubig unya mo absorb jud ba pagkadlawon ko mag study maong dira na jud nako gina schedule akua kaugalingon.” (FGD-04)

(When you wake up early in the morning, your mind is at its freshest, like a sponge ready to absorb information. Recognizing this, I schedule my study time for the early morning hours.)

Furthermore, FGD-07 employs a strategy of setting study time at night, utilizing a timer to maintain focus and reduce distractions during preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. This approach allows her to create a structured and efficient study environment. By setting a specific timeframe for studying, individuals can enhance their concentration and minimize interruptions. She noted:

“Sa ako pod no is kay pag gabii pero naga timer ko, mag timer so kani ok mag study ko focus lang walay cellphone pag mo tingog na kay mag cellphone kadali hing ana lang.” (FGD-07)

(For me, at night, I rely on a timer. I set it to ensure I remain focused solely on studying, without any distractions from my cellphone. When the timer goes off, I stop immediately, as I know how easily the cellphone can lead to distractions.)

Establishing Goals for Inspiration. The second code of the probed issue. According to the participants establishing goals in studying for the licensure examination for teachers provides direction, motivation, and a sense of accomplishment. Breaking down preparation into manageable tasks and tracking progress along the way can maximize chances of success on the exam.

Likewise, FGD-03 articulates that setting a specific goal, such as passing the LET, helps maintain focus and increases motivation to study harder. By having a clear objective, individuals can direct their efforts more effectively. Additionally, the desire to achieve the goal can significantly boost one's motivation. Ultimately, this strategy fosters a more disciplined and dedicated study routine, enhancing

the likelihood of success. She stated:

“Motivation pod nako sa akoo kaugalingon nga dapat naa jud koy goal like makapasara ka ng specific goal kung unsa jud ang ako gusto e achieve ani naa ba koy plano nga pasaron or magpabilin ba ko ka ganing pag huna-hunaon nako akoo goal mas pursigido ko mag study.” (FGD-03)

(Motivation comes from within, urging me to set clear goals, define what I truly want to achieve. Do I have a plan to succeed, or will I merely ponder my goals? The more determined I am, the more committed I become to studying.)

Moreover, self-encouragement drives IDI-02 to work diligently, with the ultimate goal of passing the LET as a milestone and a gateway to unlocking countless opportunities and achieving her dreams. Each step forward, fueled by her unwavering determination, transforms success from a mere possibility into an inevitable outcome. The journey toward passing the exam is seen as more than just a requirement it is a critical step toward realizing her full potential and fulfilling her aspirations. She stated:

“Gina encourage lang nako akoang kaugalingon nga kaya nako ni despite sa mga challenges nga akoang na encounter, tungod kay naa koy goal which is maka pasar tuod dili lalim labi nag magsabay na tanan imoha buhatunon unya mag study paka ug pero naa man koy goal nga gusto nako makab-ot maningkamot jud ko.” (IDI-02)

(I encourage myself that I can do this despite the challenges I encounter because I have a goal, which is to pass. It is not easy, especially when everything piles up and I have to study, but I have a goal that I want to achieve, so I strive for it.)

In addition, IDI-03 underscores the significance of being motivated to study harder with the clear goal of passing the licensure examination for teachers. Having a specific objective provides direction and purpose, which are essential for maintaining focus. This clear goal can serve as a powerful motivator, driving individuals to put in the necessary effort and dedication. The determination to achieve this goal can enhance both the quality and consistency of study sessions. She mentioned that:

“Basta mga board exam na gani wala man juy sayon no pero ug mag set gani ka sa imo kaugalingon ug goal nga gusto ko maka pasar bisag ang process ug ang preparation dili lalim grabi ang ka lisud ng ana ma agian nako mag pursigi jud ko kay mao mani akoo gusto mahitabo ug mao mani akoo goal.” (IDI-03)

(When it comes to board exams, nothing is easy. However, if you set a goal for yourself to pass, even though the process and preparation are difficult, you will persevere because that is what you want to achieve, and it is your goal.)

Engaging in Hobbies and Interest. The third code of the probed issue. According to the participants, taking breaks to engage in hobbies or interests serves as a vital tool to alleviate stress and prevent burnout during intense study sessions. This intentional relaxation revitalizes your mind, fostering a sense of well-being that translates into heightened focus and productivity in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Likewise, IDI-06 finds relief from stress while studying for the licensure examination for teachers by playing chess and other online games. The pressure of reviewing for such a significant test can be overwhelming, but engaging in these activities provides a much-needed mental break. Chess, with its strategic demands, offers a way to shift focus and challenge the mind in a different way. Similarly, other online games serve as an escape, allowing for relaxation and a bit of fun amidst the study grind. He stated that:

“In terms of managing my stress when studying I stopped for a while and I do my hobbies also like playing chess or other online games in order to refresh my mind and after that back to study so that’s the usual routine I do.” (IDI- 06)

(In terms of managing my stress while studying, I take a break and engage in my hobbies, such as playing chess or other online games, to refresh my mind. After that, I return to studying. That is my usual routine.)

Furthermore, IDI-04 recognizes the significance of allocating time to engage in writing as a means to redirect stress and relieve pressure from studying in preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. The act of writing offers a creative outlet that contrasts the rigid structure of exam preparation. This practice not only helps her manage stress but also enhances her overall well-being She stated that:

“Mag a lot kog time na mag me time ko unya mag sulat-sulat ug mga biskan unsa kay mao ra may makalipay sa akoo basta mangita kog ways nga ma re-direct nako akoang stress and ma relieve nako to siya nga pressure so sa paagi sa like pagbuhat ug mga hobbies nako hing ana.” (IDI-04)

(I allocate time for myself to write anything because that brings me joy, especially when I am looking for ways to redirect my stress and relieve pressure. That is how I do it, by engaging in my hobbies.)

Similarly, immersing oneself in games, movies, or dramas to effectively unwind and alleviate the stress from licensure examination for teachers' preparation according to IDI-05. The mental escape provided by these activities offers a break from the constant pressure of studying. Games challenge the mind in a fun and engaging manner, movies transport viewers to different worlds, and dramas provide emotional experiences that can be cathartic. He stated that:

“Dili jud all the time nga mag sige ko ug study I have to give something pod para sa akoo sarili through entertain myself sa games sa

mga movies or unsa ban ga films or dramas kay lisud man nga ihatag nako tanan ang time sap ag study sa preparation for LET basin mawala ko sa akona kaugalingon.” (IDI-05)

(It is not always possible for me to keep studying. I also need to take some time for myself, indulging in activities like playing games, watching movies, or enjoying dramas. Dedication solely to studying for LET preparation is challenging, as I might lose myself in the process.)

Conditioning and Preparing Oneself. The third coping mechanism of fourth-year teacher education students aligns with their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers and seems to be influenced by similar responses from the participants. They emphasize the time dedicated to physical activity not only contributes to a healthier body but also fosters a healthier mind. Engaging in physical exercise stimulates brain function and cognition, potentially reducing anxieties and worries associated with licensure examination for teachers preparation.

Ensuring Adequate Rest and Well-Balanced Meals. This is the first code of the third probed issue. According to the participants, maintaining proper nutrition plays a key role in their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. They believe that by consuming a balanced diet rich in essential nutrients, the brain is better equipped to function at its highest capacity. This, in turn, enhances cognitive abilities such as focus, memory retention, and problem-solving skills, all of which are critical for effective learning. Participants noted that proper nutritional support provides them with sustained energy throughout their study sessions, helping them remain alert and productive. Moreover, they emphasized that a healthy diet not only boosts brain function but also supports overall physical well-being, which is crucial in managing the stress and demands of preparing for the licensure exam. By prioritizing a balanced diet, participants feel more confident in their ability to study effectively and perform well on the exam.

Likewise, IDI-03 shares that embracing moments of rest ensures that the mind is revitalized, enabling one to approach studies with renewed vigor and clarity. Taking regular breaks allows the brain to process information more effectively, preventing burnout and maintaining motivation. Rest periods can include activities such as napping, meditating, or simply taking a walk, all of which contribute to mental well-being. She states:

“Binibigyan ko ang aking sarili ng isang araw o ilang oras na ipahinga ang aking katawan pati na rin ang aking utak dahil gamit na gamit talaga ang aking katawan lalo na pag mas binigyan ko ng mahabang oras ang pag review dahil minsan ay nawawala ako sa aking balanse. Kung hindi ko ipapahinga ang akong buong katawan mahihirapan akong iproseso ang mga kaalaman na aking nakukuhha mula sa pinag-aaralan.” (IDI-03)

(I give myself a day or a few hours to rest my body as well as my mind because I become really exhausted, especially after spending long hours reviewing. Sometimes, I lose my balance. If I do not rest my entire body, I will struggle to process the knowledge I acquire from studying.)

Moreover, FGD-05 emphasizes the importance of maintaining good health to alleviate stress during the review for the licensure examination for teachers. Proper nutrition, regular exercise, and sufficient sleep play crucial roles in supporting both physical and mental well-being. Prioritizing wellness ensures that individuals are in the best possible condition to face the demands of exam preparation, leading to better performance and outcomes. She stated that:

“So pag stress na jud ko sa akong hing-ani preparation sa LET ako ra jung always ginabuhay is matulog ug mokaon. Always jud ka ng gina ingon sa akona na matulog jud mokaon kay health baya jud akong puhunan so dapat mao jud atoang tagaan ug time.” (FGD-05)

(When I become really stressed about my preparation for the LET, what I always do is simply sleep and eat. People often remind me to prioritize sleep and nutrition because my health is truly important; it is my investment. Therefore, I should prioritize it and allocate time accordingly.)

Furthermore, IDI-01 emphasizes the importance of managing stress during preparation for the licensure examination for teachers by prioritizing regular meals and ensuring adequate sleep. Consistent and nutritious meals provide the energy needed to sustain long study sessions and maintain focus. Adequate sleep is crucial for cognitive function, memory retention, and overall well-being. By balancing diet and rest, she can better cope with the pressures of her review. She expressed:

“Sa akona kay ang pag manage sa akong stress ug pag maintain sa akong healthy balance between sa pag study for preparation is kaon lang jud ko and then tulog I mean mokaon sa tamang oras bahalag ginagmay basta naay sulod akong tiyan kay ang importante na para naa poy sulod akong utok dapat naa poy sulod akona tiyan and matulog ug sayu like mga 9 pm payts na na siya ug gusto ka mag study pa.” (IDI-01)

(For me, managing my stress and maintaining a healthy balance while preparing for study simply involves eating and then sleeping. I mean, eating at the right times, even if it is just a little, as long as there is something in my stomach because what is important is that there is something in my stomach so there can be something in my mind. I also sleep early, around 9 PM, when everything is already settled, if I still want to study.)

Additionally, FGD-02 ensures eating at the appropriate times to facilitate effective LET preparation. Proper meal timing helps maintain energy levels throughout the day, which is crucial for long study sessions. By scheduling meals strategically, students can avoid energy

crashes and maintain consistent focus. Eating at appropriate times becomes an integral part of a balanced routine, enhancing the overall effectiveness of LET preparation. She stated:

“Akoa pag mag study ko whole day dili nako kalimtan ang mokaon sa tamang oras kay para ano unsa may studyhan sad nako ug dili ko mokaon mosakit ra akoa tiyan ma stress na hinuon ko.” (FGD-02)

(When I study for the whole day, I never forget to eat at the right times because otherwise, my stomach will ache and I will get stressed, which will affect my studying.)

Seek God’s Intervention. The second code of the third probed issue. According to the participants, the most important aspect that every LET-taker would never forget is to seek God’s intervention. Most of the participants, sought spiritual guidance, sustained devotions, and prayer support. They believed that praying reduced the stress, nervousness, and pressure. They also assumed that in God’s perfect time and by his grace and blessings, they would pass the LET.

Likewise, IDI-01 embraces divine guidance and strength from God while studying for the licensure examination for teachers. This spiritual support is essential for maintaining unwavering focus and determination. By seeking divine help, she finds the motivation to persevere through challenging study sessions. Letting faith fuel her preparation instills a sense of purpose and calm. According to her:

“Ka ng naa man juy time ba nga wala nako kabalo sa akoa buhatunon mawala nako halos dili nako ka study ka ng bug at na jud kaau akoa feelings mag ampo jud ko mangayu kog guidance ug dungag kusog kung naa may mga worries sa life then let the universe and God decide.” (IDI-01)

(When I reach a point where I am unsure of what to do, I almost lose my ability to study and feel quite low. During such moments, I turn to prayer, seeking guidance and extra strength, particularly when life’s worries weigh heavily on me. Then, I let the universe and God decide.)

Moreover, FGD-01 fully embraces the power of surrendering everything to God, viewing this act not merely as a source of comfort but as an essential practice during the demanding process of preparing for the licensure examination for teachers (LET). She believes that entrusting her worries, stress, and uncertainties to God allows her to release the immense pressure she faces. By placing her trust in divine guidance, she feels a sense of peace, reassurance, and inner strength, which helps her navigate the challenges of exam preparation with a clearer mind and renewed focus. For her, faith is a powerful force that transforms anxiety into perseverance and guides her toward achieving her goal. She expressed that:

“Always jud mag Pray mao na ang akong pinaka-una nga buhaton e open nako akoa mind ug heart e surrender nako tanan kay God ipagawas nako akoa gibati sa iyaha mga ka guol ug syempre guidance ug wisdom.” (FGD-01)

(I begin with prayer, as it is my initial step. I open my mind and heart, relinquishing everything to God. I confide in Him my feelings of sadness and, of course, seek His guidance and wisdom.)

Furthermore, FGD-04 engages in conversation with God to seek guidance for licensure examination for teachers review preparation. By opening her heart and mind, she invites divine wisdom and direction into her journey. This spiritual practice ensures that every step is guided by His infinite knowledge and grace. With this divine support, she feels more confident and prepared for the exam. She mentioned:

“Tapos ayaw kalimte e talk c God naa man gud time maka ingon ka sa iyaha na Lord tabangi ko ana nalang jud.” (FGD- 04)

(Then, remember to talk to God, there are moments when you can say to Him, 'Lord, please help me with this.)

Obtaining Multi-Faceted Forms of Support from Peers and Family. This is the last essential theme for the coping mechanism of fourth-year teacher education students about their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. Based on the collective input from the participants regarding the second research question, it was found that another coping mechanism of fourth-year teacher education students is to seek support from peers and family. They were provided with multi-faceted forms of support in preparation for licensure examinations for teachers. The participants considered these supports as very important and helpful to them in facing the challenges of the LET preparation.

Colleague and Mentor Support. Is the first code for the fourth probed issue. During the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, participants conveyed that valuing the social support coming from their friends, colleagues, and instructors which they considered very important in their journey during LET preparation. These supports were in the form of tangible assistance like review materials and prayers, advice, practical test-taking tips, and emotional. It helped them reduce the amount of stress they experienced, elevated their confidence during the preparation and helped them cope better in dealing with stressful situations.

Similarly, IDI-05 actively seeks assistance from mentors and friends, recognizing their pivotal role in the journey toward LET excellence. These individuals offer invaluable guidance, drawing from their own experiences and expertise. Their support is instrumental in navigating the complexities of exam preparation. This collaborative effort enhances understanding and boosts confidence, ultimately fostering a more effective and successful preparation experience. He mentioned that:

“Sa amoa mentor syempre sa content matters sa mga lessons sa subject matter dako kaau ilaha help kay sila man ang expertise ana and they are sharing knowledge sa amoa how to ace the licensure examination for teachers and sa classmates nako and friends pod at the same time sabay sa Let mag study kauban sila mag review.” (IDI-05)

(In our mentor, especially in the content matters of the lessons in the subject matter, their help is immense because they are the experts in that field and they are sharing their knowledge with us on how to ace the licensure examination for teachers. Also, my classmates, friends, and I study and review together for the LET.)

Additionally, IDI-01 seeks support from mentors and classmates, recognizing the value of their input in enhancing preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. By offering strategies and facilitating the exchange of ideas, these individuals contribute to a more comprehensive review process. Engaging with mentors and peers helps to identify effective study methods and address any gaps in knowledge. Together, this support network plays a crucial role in achieving success in the licensure examination. She mentioned:

“Sa among mentor, after every review, mohatag sila ug 1-150 item drills ug tagaan mi ug oras para mag-answer. Human ana, mag-checking ug mag-rationalize si mentor, gatudlo sa strategies para sa general ug professional education. Usahay, mag-review ko kauban akong friends, mag-exchange mi ug ideas.” (IDI-01)

(Our mentor gives us 1-150 item drills after every review, and we are given time to answer. After that, we check our answers, and the mentor explains the rationale, teaching strategies for general and professional education. Sometimes, I review with my friends, and we exchange ideas.)

Furthermore, IDI-02 actively seeks support from friends, who serve as indispensable allies in her preparation for the licensure examination for teachers (LET). These friends provide assistance not only as study partners but also as mentors, guiding her through essential learning strategies and key concepts. Their collaboration is invaluable, as they help clarify complex topics and offer insights that might otherwise be difficult to grasp alone. Beyond academic support, these friends help maintain her motivation and morale by fostering a collaborative and encouraging study environment. Their guidance, combined with a supportive network, significantly strengthens her preparation efforts. She stated that:

“My friends support and help me in my preparation for Let by being my study-buddies and sa amoa mentor nga gina guide me sa mga strategies and concepts na dapat namong ma tun an.” (IDI-02)

(My friends support and assist me in my LET preparation by serving as my study buddies, and our mentor guides me through the strategies and concepts that we need to learn.)

Family Emotional Cohesion and Support. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. According to the participants' feedback from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, varied support coming from loved ones are essential factors in not to give up during their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. These were emotional supports like comforting words, moral and spiritual support, warmth, and care. Additionally, they were also provided with esteem support such as motivation, reassurance, and encouragement and instrumental support like the provision of financial assistance.

Similarly, IDI-06 expressed that his parents provide crucial emotional support by being understanding, patient, and encouraging during this stressful time. Their words of motivation help to boost his morale and keep him focused. When challenges arise, they offer a listening ear, providing comfort and practical advice. This unwavering support is essential for navigating the pressures of preparation and maintaining a positive outlook. He stated:

“After knowing that I'm already in my CSA preparation for my Licensure examination for teachers my family really boost my confidence by supporting me all the way, they support me morally and financially so that I will be able to lighten the burden from the review.” (IDI-06)

(After learning that I am already in the process of preparing for my Licensure Examination for Teachers, my family significantly boosted my confidence by supporting me every step of the way. They provided both moral and financial support to help ease the burden of the review.)

Moreover, IDI-04 expressed that her family serves as the primary support system throughout her preparation for the licensure examination for teachers. Their encouragement and understanding are pivotal in managing the stress and demands of studying. Emotional support from her family provides reassurance and motivation during challenging times. She states that:

“Ang akong family mao jud ang akong support system. Bisan mag-breakdown ko tungod sa LET preparation, sila ang nag-push ug nag-support. Ginatagaan ko nila ug time para maka-rest, dili ko nila ginapabuhay ug trabaho kay kabalo sila na stress ko. Grabe ka supportive akong family, ug dako kaayo ilang tabang para ma-relax ug ma-condition akong utok sa review” (IDI-04)

(My family is truly my support system. Even when I break down due to LET preparation, they push and support me. They give me time to rest and do not assign me any tasks because they understand the stress. My family is very supportive, and their help is significant for me to relax and prepare my mind for the review.)

Furthermore, IDI-01 emphasized that her family is a significant source of motivation during her preparation for the licensure

examination for teachers. They continually remind her of the importance of maintaining determination and resilience. Their encouragement helps her stay focused and committed to her study goals. Through both words and actions, her family reinforces the value of perseverance in the face of challenges. She stated that:

“Sa family naman sila ang naga hatag ug kadasig para hawdon nako sa tanan ang exam sila naghatag ug kusog para mopadayon labi na kung usahay maka feel kog breakdowns, naga motivate sa akoo, sila ang naga pahinumdom nga kailangan jud ko mo dasig perme.” (IDI-01)

(In my family, they are the ones who provide me with the strength to face the exam head-on. They give me the motivation to keep going, especially when I sometimes feel like breaking down. They remind me that I need to persevere constantly.)

Additionally, DI-02 is motivated by family to believe in her ability to review effectively for the licensure examination for teachers. Their encouragement helps build her confidence and reinforces her belief in her own capabilities. By providing consistent support and positive affirmations, her family plays a key role in boosting her self-assurance. Their faith in her potential inspires her to stay dedicated and persistent throughout the preparation process. She expressed that:

“Gina-motivate ko nil ana makaya ra nako ang pag-review. They are my support system kay in times nga negative na kaayo ko dili nila malimtan na ipa-feel at ease ko nga okay ra tanan wala pud ko gina-pressure sa akoo family.” (IDI-02)

(They motivate me that I can handle the review. They are my support system because in times when I feel very negative, they never fail to make me feel at ease that everything is okay, and I'm not pressured by my family.)

Finally, FGD-01 is motivated to work diligently in preparing for the licensure examination for teachers through encouragement and support from parents. Their unwavering belief in her abilities and consistent reinforcement of her efforts provide a strong foundation for her studies. The emotional and practical support they offer helps her stay focused and committed to her preparation. According to the statement:

“Ang akoo ginikanan syempre e remind man jud ta murag ginakuan ko ni mama ba ka ng pasaron para dili masayang ka ng e motivate ko niya kay syempre para mani sa akoang kaugmaon ka ng mura gani ug maningkamot pod ko ug maayo kay in terms of financial kay mangita pod sila ug paraan kay dili baya makahiram sa laing tao murag sila mama nalang nga mangitag paraan na ma kuanan ang financial sa akoo mag review.” (FGD-01)

(My parents always remind me, just like my mother, who asks if I will pass so that my efforts will not go to waste. She motivates me because this is for my future, so I strive hard, especially in financial terms. They find ways to support me since we cannot borrow from others; it is mostly my mother who finds ways to provide financial assistance for my review.)

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers among fourth-year teacher education students in a local college utilizes a mixed methods approach, employing the convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves corroborating the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases. Table 5 outlines the salient quantitative and qualitative findings, presenting focal points in the first column, which contains the aspect of focal points of the study. This is followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third columns, respectively. The findings from the quantitative phase typically consist of the items in each indicator, while the qualitative findings, which display the identified responses, confirm or disconfirm the quantitative results. The fourth column indicates the nature of the data integration, and the fifth column contains the axiological implications based on the data described in the presenting columns.

Table 4. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect for Focal Points	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Data Integration	Axiology Implications
Students' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in terms of personal aspect	Table 2 on the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers in terms of personal aspect item no. 4 having a strong desire to achieve my goals and excel academically so that I can pass the LET exam with a mean of 4.49 which rated as high	Table 4 on the lived experiences and coping mechanisms shared by students with regard to the preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers has a code of academic accountability highlighting the essential themes of attending regularly the review session and classes to enhance one's knowledge	Merging-Converging	Students who have a strong desire to achieve their goals and excel academically to pass the LET attend regular review sessions and classes to enhance their knowledge
Students' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in terms	Table 2 on the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers in terms of environmental aspect no. 5	Table 4 on the lived experiences and coping mechanisms shared by students with regard to the preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers has a	Merging-Converging	Students who are willing to receive positive support and attitudes from friends and family knows the important role

of environmental aspect	willing to receive support and positive attitudes from friends and family with a mean of 4.44 which rated as very high	code of colleague and mentor support and family emotional cohesion and support highlighting the essential theme of obtaining multi-faceted forms of support from peers and family		of multi-faceted forms of support from peers and family in studying for licensure examination for teachers' preparation
Students' preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers in terms of instructional aspect	Table 2 on the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers in terms of instructional aspect no. 1 using review materials provided by our school with a mean of 4.34 which rated as very high	Table 4 on the lived experiences and coping mechanisms shared by students with regard to the preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers has a code of compiling study materials from review session/CSA subjects highlighting the essential theme of feeling not equipped with knowledge and skills resulting to acquisition of review materials	Merging-Converging	Students use review materials provided by the school by compiling them from review sessions and CSA subjects to supplement their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers

Teacher Education Student's Preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers in terms of Instructional Aspect. In quantitative phase, item number 1 on the instructional aspect using review materials provided by our school has a mean of 4.34 with a description of very high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is code compiling study materials from review session/CSA subjects. From an axiological perspective, the students use review materials provided by the school by compiling them from review sessions and CSA subjects to supplement their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Intervention Scheme

The findings of this study highlight the importance of equipping fourth-year teacher education students to be fully committed and to have effective time management in their review sessions, while also drawing encouragement, support, and motivation from both peers and family members as they prepare for the licensure examination for teachers. Commitment workshops are recommended as an intervention scheme because they help students understand the significance of their commitments. By discussing the importance of staying committed to their studies, students become more aware of the impact their choices have on their academic success. Encouraging students to write down specific obligations related to their licensure examination for teachers' preparation is a practical strategy. When commitments are documented, they become more tangible and real. Students can refer back to these written obligations as a reminder during challenging moments.

On the other hand, Time Management Seminars are essential interventions for enhancing students' practical time management skills, students can learn to allocate time for licensure examinations for teacher's review sessions. Students learn various strategies to boost productivity, such as the Pomodoro Technique, which promotes focused work sessions followed by short breaks. Additionally, time-blocking methods are introduced to help students organize their schedules and prioritize tasks efficiently.

Additionally, Family Peer Support Workshops involve training family members to become peer supporters who can offer encouragement, motivation, and emotional support to students. When family members understand the stress and pressure students face, they can provide empathy, encouragement, and a listening ear. This emotional support can help students stay motivated and resilient as they get ready for the teacher licensing exam. Overall, these intervention schemes provide fourth-year teacher education students with commitment and time management skills through workshops, seminars, and family support initiatives, thereby fostering a supportive environment and practical strategies that enhance their preparation for the licensure examination for teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the level of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers is very high in terms of personal aspect, environmental aspect and instructional aspect. Hence, this indicate that the following indicators are always manifested by the selected fourth-year teacher education students.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based from the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The results gave more information about the lived experiences and coping mechanism of fourth-year teacher education in terms of their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. Qualitatively, the fourth-year teacher education students experienced different challenges that affects their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. The following terms emerged: Feeling Not Equipped with Knowledge and Skills Resulting to Acquisition of Review Materials, Lacking of Time Management Between Social Media and Academic Responsibilities, Having Difficulty in Understanding Text due to Poor Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary, and Experiencing Challenges in Achieving Academic Grade Competency.

Third, from the participants responses other themes are identified which shows the coping mechanism offourth-year teacher education

students with regard to their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers. The following are the themes: Attending Regularly the Review Session and Classes to Enhance One's Knowledge, Engaging to Various Strategies for Effective Academic Achievement, Conditioning and Preparing Oneself, and Obtaining Multi-Faceted Forms of Support from Peers and Family.

Lastly, to better understand the preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both findings from the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The status of preparedness of teacher education students for the licensure examination for teachers based on the quantitative results shows that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both of the quantitative and qualitative results confirms that despite the challenges experienced by the fourth-year teacher education students in their preparedness for the licensure examination for teachers they can overcome those challenges.

References

- Abao, E., Petancio, J., Sanchez, J., & Sumalinog, J. (2023). Performance of beginning teachers in the licensure examination for teachers: A national study. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1240658>
- Alenezi, W., & Brinhaupt, T. M. (2022). The use of social media as a tool for learning: Perspectives of students in the faculty of education at Kuwait University. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 14(1), ep340. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/11476>
- Alharbi, M. A. (2018). Reading strategies, learning styles, and reading comprehension: A correlation study. *Journal of Language Teaching & Research*, 6(6).
- Amanonce, J., & Maramag, R. (2020). Licensure examination performance and academic achievement of teacher education graduates. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 9(3), 510–516. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v9i3.20614>
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. American Psychological Association.
- Bellen, J., Abela, R., & Truya, R. (2018). Academic achievement as a predictor in the performance of licensure examination for teachers. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 5(1).
- Binayao, B. S., & Dales, Z. I. (2020). A phenomenological study of the passers and non-passers in the licensure examination for teachers. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*.
- Braat-Eggen, E., Reinten, J., Hornikx, H., & Kohlrausch, A. (2021). The effect of background noise on a "studying for an exam" task in an open-plan study environment: A laboratory study. *Frontiers in Built Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2021.687087>
- Burbano, R. O., Luna, C. A. R., & Riascos, Y. V. (2018). Family support factor in relation to the academic performance of students from El Tablón Panamericano, Taminango. *Revista UNIMAR*, 36(2), 15–28.
- Burbano, R. O., Luna, C. A. R., & Riascos, Y. V. (2018). Family support factor in relation to the academic performance of students from El Tablón Panamericano, Taminango. *Revista UNIMAR*, 36(2), 15–28.
- Burston, M. A. (2018). I work and don't have time for that theory stuff: Time poverty and higher education. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 41(4), 516–529.
- Cabahug, M. M., Bonghanoy, S. M. A., Tubog Jr, J., Asingua, A. B., Chen, Q., & Tul-id, C. S. (2024). Graduates are failing in the examination: An ethical investigation on the experiences of board licensure examination for professional teachers (BLEPT) takers. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 3(2), 1–6.
- Cahapay, M. (2021). System admission test and licensure examination for teachers: The case of passed and conditional groups. *College of Education, Mindanao State University*. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v17i4.9809>
- Canete, O. (2021). When expressions of faith in the Philippines becomes a potential COVID-19 'superspreader'. *ResearchGate*.
- Castellino, D. R., & Bharath, S. (2019). Role of social support in academic achievement. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 10(2), 249–254.
- Cayabas Jr, J. P., & Sumeg-ang, D. A. (2023). Challenges and interventions in developing instructional materials: Perspectives of public school teachers in basic education. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 6(4), 849–855.
- Chukwu, C., Aroh, P., Ozor, T., Ugwoezuonu, A., & Zema, O. (2022). Influence of social media usage on time management of social science education students in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *Webology*, 19(3).
- Clair-Christman, J. S. (2018). Family support and institutional support for low-income, first-generation college students. *University of Delaware*.
- Cohen, S., & Wills, T. A. (1985). The role of social support in mediating stress and illness. *Psychological Bulletin*, 98(2), 310–357.
- Colicol, F., Puig, C., & Judan, S. (2022). Evaluation of university review program for teachers' licensure examination: A transformative

mixed methods study using Bourdieu-Scheerens framework. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(1), 277-300. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.1.16>

Creswell, J. (2013). *Qualitative research in corporate communication*. Blogs Baruch.

Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Pearson Education, Incorporated.

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson/Merrill Education.

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum.

Dela Rosa, R., & Vargas, D. (2021). The licensure examination for teachers performance of education graduates: The CLSU experience. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3817306>

Delos Angeles, M. (2020). Predictors of performance in licensure examination for teachers. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 835-843. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080314>

Elleman, A. M., & Oslund, E. L. (2019). Reading comprehension research: Implications for practice and policy. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 6(1), 3-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732218816339>

Festinger, L. (1957). Cognitive dissonance theory. *Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8>

Firat, M., Kılınc, H., & Yüzer, T. V. (2018). Level of intrinsic motivation of distance education students in e-learning environments. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 34(1), 63-70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12214>

Frigillano, S., Examen, S., & Nulada, L. (2018). Pre-service teachers' anxiety and preparation prior to board examination. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 6(1), 209-216.

Gilavand, A., & Jamshidnezhad, A. (2018). The effect of noise in educational institutions on learning and academic achievement of elementary students in Ahvaz, South West of Iran. <https://www.sid.ir/en/Journal/ViewPaper.aspx?ID=488348>

Grégoire, S., Chénier, C., Doucerain, M., Lachance, L., & Shankland, R. (2020). Ecological momentary assessment of stress, well-being, and psychological flexibility among college and university students during acceptance and commitment therapy. *Canadian Journal of Behavioural Science*, 52(3), 231-243.

Hillman, C. H., Erickson, K. I., & Kramer, A. F. (2018). Be smart, exercise your heart: Exercise effects on brain and cognition. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 9(1), 58-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17518420801997007>

Hu, S., & McCormick, A. C. (2018). An engagement model of academic success for underrepresented minority students. *Journal of College Student Development*, 53(1), 42-60. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2012.0003>

Hurd, E., Brinegar, K. M., & Harrison, L. M. (2023). Renewing the commitment for specialized middle grades teacher preparation and licensure. *Middle School Journal*, 54(2), 2-4.

Irene, E. (2023). Evaluation of teacher education curricula and its relevance to licensure examination using Context, Input, Process, and Product (CIPP) model. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 8(1), 100607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100607>

Kim, S., Raza, M., & Seidman, E. (2019). Improving 21st-century teaching skills: The key to effective 21st-century learners. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 14(1), 99-117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745499919829214>

Koçak, O., Ak, N., Erdem, S. S., Sinan, M., Younis, M. Z., & Erdoğan, A. (2021). The role of family influence and academic satisfaction on career decision-making self-efficacy and happiness. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 5919. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115919>

Valle, A. M., & Brobo, M. A. (2022). A comparative study in the performance of the first takers of the licensure examination for teachers (LET): An action research. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 10(3), 778-781.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jeanne I. Bersabal

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines

Evelyn E. Cañete, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines